

DECEMBER 2023

VOLUME 40

ISSN 0067-9208

INDAGO

**Investigating nature
and humanity in Africa**

Published for the National Museum, Bloemfontein

INDAGO

Investigating nature and humanity in Africa

Published annually for the National Museum, Bloemfontein

Indago is a DHET-accredited, diamond open access journal that seeks to promote knowledge of natural and cultural heritage by publishing high-quality, peer-reviewed scientific research. Previously known as *Navorsing van die Nasionale Museum*, *Indago* is published for the National Museum, Bloemfontein, South Africa. Manuscripts relevant to all topics of the natural and human sciences in Africa are accepted, including but not limited to botany, zoology, palaeontology, archaeology, anthropology, history and fine arts. Accepted articles are first published online, freely accessible through the journal's webpage. Hardcopy issues are printed yearly. Authors will bear full responsibility for the factual content of their publications, and opinions expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the National Museum. All manuscripts will be critically reviewed by at least two appropriate external referees. Contributions should be addressed to The Editor-in-Chief, *Indago*, National Museum, Bloemfontein, and sent by e-mail to indago@nasmus.co.za. Instructions to authors appear at the back of each volume and are also available on *Indago* Website.

Editor-in-Chief

Mike Mostovski (PhD, PIN RAS), National Museum, Bloemfontein

Associate Editors

Natural Sciences: Gimo M. Daniel (PhD, UP), Terrestrial Invertebrates, National Museum, Bloemfontein

Human Sciences: Derek Du Bruyn (PhD, UFS), History Department, National Museum, Bloemfontein

External Editor

Hendrik Snyders (PhD, Stellenbosch), Centre for Military Studies, South African Military Academy, Saldanha

Consulting Editors

Prof. C. Chimimba (Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of Pretoria, South Africa)

Dr J. Deacon (South African Heritage Resources Agency, Cape Town, South Africa – retired)

Dr A. Dippenaar-Schoeman (ARC – Plant Protection Research Institute, Pretoria, South Africa – retired)

Dr A. Kemp (Ditsong National Museum of Natural History, Pretoria, South Africa – retired)

Dr D.T. Rowe-Rowe (Ezemvelo KZN Wildlife, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa – retired)

Prof. B.S. Rubidge (University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa – retired)

Prof. A.E. van Wyk (Department of Botany, University of Pretoria, South Africa)

Prof. A. Wessels (Department of History, University of the Free State, Bloemfontein, South Africa)

Layout

Carien van Eck, Design Department, National Museum, Bloemfontein

Hard copies of *Indago* are available from the Library at the National Museum, P.O. Box 266, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa. Free access to electronic copies (PDF) via the *Indago* Website: <https://nationalmuseumpublications.co.za>.

Cover illustration

A typical English-style semi-vernacular or “hybrid” topiary garden with a simple formal axial layout, Moiloa Street, Batho, 2009. Note the ivy-covered arch and wire netting fence.

(National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 80)

© 2023 National Museum, Bloemfontein (journal)

© 2023 Authors (individual articles)

ISSN 0067-9208

ISBN 978-1-86847-189-8

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11643185

EDITORIAL

The modern ecumene is often referred to as the VUCA world, instilled with Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity. Such liminal feelings and perceptions are, however, hardly novel, for already Sallust noted, albeit in reference to a particular case of an attempted coup d'état by Catiline, that “*repente omnis tristitia invasit: festinare, trepidare, neque loco neque homini cuiquam satis credere, neque bellum gerere neque pacem habere, suo quisque metu pericula metiri*” [suddenly sorrow spread over all; they became anxious and agitated, they trusted enough neither any place nor any person, they neither waged war nor enjoyed peace, each measured the danger by his own fear]. Constantly changing are not only people and human societies but the Nature itself, which biodiversity and climatic perturbations have been reasonably well documented in its half-a-billion-year-long palaeontological and geological record. If anything else can offer us a subtle sense of stability, natural and cultural history museums would be among those sanctuaries where we can escape from and reflect upon our precarious environments, and learn lessons. Among the core museum activities—scientific, curatorial and educational—museum journals occupy a special niche, serving as archives to preserve and authoritative channels to convey specialist interpretations of natural objects and cultural artifacts.

I am honored and humbled to be invited to join my colleagues Drs Derek Du Bruyn, Hendrik Snyders and Gimo Daniel in the editorial team of *Indago*, and to ensure that the journal maintains its high academic standard and refines its compliance with the best practices as outlined by the Academy of Science of South Africa, Department of Higher Education and Training, and international scholarly publishers at large. In 2023, we have substantially reworked our Instructions to Authors making them more detail-oriented. We have also drafted several other policies—Editorial Ethics & Malpractice Statement, Copyright and Licensing Statement, Privacy Statement, and Disclaimer—for the benefit of our authors, readers and the journal itself. All these documents are available on the *Indago* Website.

From this year, final versions of individual articles are, and will be, published online first ahead of finalizing the entire volume. This up-to-date approach pursues faster turnaround time and improves access to the journal materials and citability of papers. The page charges have been completely waived and publication of *Indago* follows now the diamond open access model. All published articles will be archived at Zenodo, which is the CERN's repository integrated with the OpenAIRE initiative; in addition to better preservation and broader visibility of the journal, such archiving is mandatory for articles in zoological taxonomy.

To summarize, *Indago* is rising to a new level and with the growing journal's portfolio it won't be too long before we see it indexed by respectable agencies like Scopus or DOAJ.

Dr Mike Mostovski (van der Brug)

Editor-in-Chief

INDAGO

DECEMBER 2023

VOLUME 40

ISSN 0067-9208

RESEARCH ARTICLES

HUMAN SCIENCES

“Garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.”: The making of Batho as a South African “garden location” with special reference to its ornamental gardens (c. 1918–1939)

D. du Bruyn 1–21

Springboks, Spitfire bows and family archery – the National Museum Bloemfontein’s Du Plessis Collection and its national and international intersections

H. Snyders 23–34

Instructions to Authors 35–38

**“Garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.”: The making of Batho as a South African “garden location”
with special reference to its ornamental gardens
(c. 1918–1939)**

Derek du Bruyn

*Department of History, National Museum, Bloemfontein, P.O. Box 266, Bloemfontein, 9300, South Africa and Research
Fellow, Department of History, University of the Free State, Bloemfontein*

E-mail: derek@nasmus.co.za

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-2357-7511>

ABSTRACT

In 1918, Batho was founded as one of South Africa’s first so-called “model locations”. In addition to sound town planning and layout, brick houses, and public amenities, Batho also became known for its “generous” plots or “garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.” and the ornamental front gardens that were laid out on them. The Bloemfontein municipality’s decision to provide residents with “garden areas” was motivated by a number of reasons, most of which were of a political nature and embedded in the segregationist ideology of the time. This article discusses the “garden areas” and the gardens that were laid out on them by Batho’s gardeners. Furthermore, the article investigates the city council’s efforts to turn the “model location” into a “garden location” and the Batho gardeners’ own efforts to this effect during the period 1918–1939. The gardeners’ front gardens resembled the English-style gardens that were popular among Bloemfontein’s whites during the 1920s and 1930s. Information obtained through archival research, field work, and oral history interviews point to the gardeners’ preference for a simple formal axial garden layout enclosed by clipped hedges and often adorned with topiary. A fondness of topiary encouraged Batho’s gardeners to create hedges, edges, and a variety of other topiary styles which had gradually evolved into a style of topiary that may be described as “township topiary”. Over time “township topiary” became a tangible expression of a unique garden identity among Batho’s gardeners. Due to the processes of acculturation and intercultural influence, which involved the Dutch, British, and African cultures, Batho’s historical and present gardens are described as semi-vernacular or “hybrid”. Most gardens display an unmistakable English cottage-garden style but a distinctly African accent is also visible.

KEYWORDS: Batho, Bloemfontein, ornamental gardens, “garden location”, “garden areas”, topiary

INTRODUCTION

Batho,¹ also known as Batho location, is Bloemfontein’s² oldest existing historically black³ township⁴ or “location”.⁵ Established in 1918, Batho is one of South Africa’s first so-called “model locations”. Apart from boasting proper town planning and layout, brick houses, public amenities, parks and squares, Batho also became known for its “generous” plots (stands) and the gardens that were laid out on them.

While black people’s garden history and gardening culture have received attention from academics in countries such as the USA,⁶ it is a neglected research field in South Africa, particularly in South African historiography. One is left with the impression that black people’s gardens and gardening culture are not worthy of academic study. As a result, only a few studies have been completed on the subject.⁷ The garden history of South African locations and townships such as Batho has been a “hidden” and “for-

1 A Sesotho word meaning “people”.

2 Also known as Mangaung. Bloemfontein forms part of the Mangaung Metropolitan Municipality.

3 In this article, the terms “black(s)” or “black people” refer to people of African origin.

4 In the South African context, the term “township” means a designated living area or suburb historically reserved for people of colour.

5 During the period of white minority rule, the term “location” was commonly used to refer to segregated informal living areas designated for people of colour, usually located on the outskirts of white towns and cities. These areas are now called “townships”.

6 For example, see R. Westmacott, *The gardens of African-Americans in the rural South*, in J.D. Hunt & J. Wolschke-Bulmahn (eds), *The vernacular garden*, pp. 77-105; B.J. Heath & A. Bennett, “The little spots allow’d them”: The archaeological study of African-American yards, *Historical Archaeology* 34(2), 2000, pp. 38-55.

7 Typically, these studies focus mostly on architecture and town planning such as R. Ginsburg, “Now I stay in a house”: Renovating the matchbox in apartheid-era Soweto, *African Studies* 55(2), 1996, pp. 127-139; D.M. Calderwood, *Native housing in South Africa*, unpublished Ph.D. thesis, *passim*.

gotten” history for the past century. This state of affairs may partially be blamed on the widespread ignorance and negative stereotypes which reinforced a historical perception, particularly among whites, that black Africans are not interested in gardening and, therefore, lack a gardening culture. The French explorer, René Caillié (1799–1838), expressed this sentiment as follows: “the natives [Africans], accustomed to live in idleness, in their hot and even scorching climate, do not trouble themselves with any thing [sic] of the kind [gardening]; the Europeans alone have gardens.”⁸ More recently, South African garden writer, Sima Eliovson (1919–1990), argued that “the history of the black population of South Africa does not reveal horticultural influences, except in their knowledge of the medicinal, poisonous and edible qualities of wild plants”.⁹

This article intends to challenge popular misconceptions and conventional understandings of black South Africans’ garden history. It is suggested that black people’s garden history and gardening culture should be considered in their own right and, therefore, should be studied on their own terms. This argument also holds for studies of black people’s garden history and gardening culture in other countries. Archival research conducted by the author on South African black people’s gardens and gardening culture revealed that, contrary to the biased views expressed in some historical sources, a gardening culture existed in Bloemfontein’s oldest locations, particularly in the old Waaihoek location,¹⁰ since the city’s pioneering years.¹¹ Although not nearly comparable to the huge and lush ornamental gardens of Bloemfontein’s white residents, the black and coloured¹² residents who lived in Waaihoek and other smaller locations¹³ laid

out both ornamental and food gardens. Waaihoek’s gardens—described as “garden patch[es]”¹⁴—had to be fitted onto “plots of land 50 x 50 [feet]”.¹⁵ By the time Batho was laid out as Bloemfontein’s new racially segregated location during the late 1910s, a gardening culture had already been established among its residents.¹⁶ This gardening culture was transferred from Waaihoek to Batho and found its expression not on “garden patches” but on “garden areas”.

The main focus of this article is the plots or “garden areas of 50 ft. [feet] by 75 ft.”¹⁷ that were provided for Batho’s residents as part of the Bloemfontein municipality’s efforts to establish Batho as a planned and orderly new location for the city’s black and coloured residents. Why were the “garden areas” provided and how did the gardens that were laid out on them look like? The focus will be on the first two decades of Batho’s existence (1918–1939), a period considered to be Batho’s “golden age”. Batho’s present gardens, many of which were laid out during the 1920s and 1930s, will be discussed in the last section to illustrate the historical continuity of the Batho gardeners’ preference for a specific garden style.

“A HIGHER STANDARD OF HOUSING”:¹⁸ THE “MODEL LOCATION” IN HISTORICAL CONTEXT

Because South Africa’s garden history and the country’s socio-political issues are interconnected, these issues and the appearance of South African gardens are also interlinked. This argument is especially applicable to South Africa’s black inha-

8 R. Caillié, *Travels through Central Africa to Timbuctoo and across the great desert, to Morocco performed in the years 1824–1828* (vol. 1), p. 161.

9 S. Eliovson, *Garden beauty of South Africa*, p. 22.

10 Initially spelt Waay Hoek, a Dutch name meaning “windy corner”.

11 Bloemfontein was established in 1846.

12 In this article, the terms “coloured(s)” or “coloured people” refer to people of mixed race and to descendents of Cape slaves, the Khoekhoen and the Khoisan.

13 For information on Bloemfontein’s oldest locations, see A.M. Sekete, *The history of the Mangaung (black) township*, unpublished M.A. mini-dissertation, pp. 2–6.

14 C.E. Hands, “Bobs” as beneficent victor: His fascinating entry into Bloemfontein, *The Bloemfontein Post*, 10.5.1900, p. 3.

15 Approximately 16.5 x 16.5 metres. Free State Provincial Archives, Bloemfontein (hereafter FSPA): A. 3(4/1) (9/2/2), Extracts: South African Races Committee: Land tenure (manuscript), p. 2.

16 For a detailed discussion of the gardens and gardening culture that existed in Bloemfontein’s oldest locations, see H.J. du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and the development of a semi-vernacular garden style in Batho, Mangaung, 1918–1939: A historical perspective*, unpublished Ph.D. thesis, pp. 262–276.

17 Approximately 16.5 x 24.75 metres. FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1919–1920, p. 8.

18 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1919–1920, p. 8.

bitants because foreign invasion, occupation, dispossession, colonialism, racism and the concomitant policies of segregation (pre-1948) and apartheid (1948–1994) severely affected their domestic environment. Therefore, Batho's garden history should firstly be viewed in the broader context of South Africa's colonisation by the Netherlands (1652–1795; 1803–1806) and Britain (1795–1803; 1806–1910) and, secondly, in the specific context of the 1920s and 1930s. Thus, Batho's gardens and their history do not stand in isolation from developments, trends and changes in garden history at local (Bloemfontein), national (South Africa) and international (Africa, Britain and Europe) levels.¹⁹

During the 1920s and 1930s South Africa was still a British dominion and, as a result, British political, social and cultural practices and preferences influenced every aspect of governance, including racial policies. Although less draconic than the apartheid policies, racially based spatial segregation was rigorously enforced by the Union²⁰ government's municipal authorities. During the period in question the idea of "home and garden" was considered the exclusive domain of whites, while black people were subjected to a position of manual and menial labour. These types of labour were mostly performed by black domestic and garden workers who maintained white-owned homes and gardens.²¹ Ironically, the racial discrimination and socio-economic deprivation from which black people suffered as a result of segregationist policies, compromised but did not prevent the development of a gardening culture and garden identity among South Africa's location residents.²²

Batho location was established in 1918 after the then Bloemfontein Town Council decided to demolish the

old Waaihoek location. At that time, Waaihoek was still the main location for Bloemfontein's black and coloured residents. The decision to demolish it was triggered by a number of factors. These included: Severe overcrowding and slum conditions which had developed in Waaihoek; the substantial growth of Bloemfontein's black and coloured population primarily due to urbanisation; and Waaihoek's close proximity to Bloemfontein's white "Town".²³ Another reason is the so-called "sanitation syndrome",²⁴ namely the perceived threat black people and their "unhygienic" living quarters posed to white people's health. The "sanitation syndrome" became an urgent issue after the Spanish Influenza epidemic of 1918 that hit Waaihoek's residents particularly hard.²⁵

A year before Batho was established the council decided that a new location had to be developed east of the Johannesburg-Cape Town railroad (Fig. 1). The railroad served as a physical barrier, which separated black Bloemfontein from its white counterpart on the basis of the government's policy of racially based territorial segregation.²⁶ On the one hand, the council saw Batho's establishment as an opportunity to resettle black and coloured people farther away from "Town" to give effect to the segregationist ideology but, on the other hand, it also wanted to establish Batho as a so-called "model location". It was no secret that Bloemfontein's council harboured ambitions for the city to become the Union's "model city". It was reasoned that, as a model location, Batho would be the model city's black equivalent and, as a result, raise the city's national profile.²⁷

While the council's model location philosophy had

19 Du Bruyn, p. 518.

20 The Union of South Africa was established in 1910.

21 S.-A. Murray, Indigenous gardening, belonging, and bewilderment: On becoming South African, in Michael Chapman (ed.), *Postcolonialism: South/African perspectives*, p. 47; S.-A. Murray, The idea of gardening: Plants, bewilderment, and indigenous identity in South Africa, *English in Africa* 33(2), October 2006, p. 52.

22 For a detailed discussion of this argument, see Du Bruyn, pp. 420-460.

23 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor's minute 1926–1927, p. 12.

24 The term was first used by historian M.W. Swanson to refer to an aspect of early 20th century segregationist thought in South Africa. For more information, see M.W. Swanson, The sanitation syndrome: Bubonic plague and urban native policy in the Cape Colony, 1900–1909, *Journal of African History* XVIII(3), 1977, pp. 387-410.

25 P. Maylam, Explaining the apartheid city: 20 years of South African urban historiography, *Journal of Southern African Studies* 21(1), March 1995, pp. 24-25; H. Phillips, The local state and public health reform in South Africa: Bloemfontein and the consequences of the Spanish 'Flu epidemic of 1918, *Journal of Southern African Studies* 13(2), January 1987, pp. 210-233.

26 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor's minute 1926–1927, p. 12.

27 D. du Bruyn, Batho celebrates a century (1918–2018): The founding of Bloemfontein's "model location", *Culina* 73, March 2019, pp. 2-3.

Figure 1: An old map of Bloemfontein shows the position of the locations in relation to the railroad track and white Bloemfontein, 1909. “Kaffir Location” north of the railroad is Waaiohoek and “Native Location” (see arrow) south of the railroad is where Batho was established in 1918. (*Souvenir programme of the South African Association for the Advancement of Science, seventh annual meeting, 27 September to 2 October 1909*)

its political undertones and ulterior motives, if only to cast the new location in a positive light, it had tangible “benefits” for Batho’s residents. In practical terms, being a model location meant that Batho’s general layout, the quality of the houses, the public amenities provided, the general administration of the

location and, importantly, the size of individual plots allocated, adhered to what was then considered to be the “best town-planning lines”.²⁸ It meant, in the segregationist language of Mayor D.A. Thomson,²⁹ that “a hygienic Native township” with “a higher standard of housing than that usually associated with locations”³⁰ was to be developed. Thomson’s mention of “a higher standard of housing” is significant. In practice, it led to the council’s implementation of the “Bloemfontein System”,³¹ which meant that residents were allowed to build their own houses with the financial assistance of the municipality.³²

Although black people were not allowed to own the plots on which their houses had been built, they were allowed to own the houses.³³ Ironically, the prospect of home ownership encouraged them to also take “ownership” of their plots, so to speak, by laying out gardens. This emphasis on beautification by laying out gardens contributed significantly to Batho’s development as a model location and, in due course, as a garden location. During the 1920s and 1930s, Bloemfontein became nationally known for its “exemplary” location and it became, to a certain extent, a “blueprint” for an idealised South African model location. Although admired for several reasons, it was indeed Batho’s layout that attracted the most attention. As will be discussed in the next section, Batho’s grid-type layout allowed for the provisioning of broad streets, generous sidewalks and, most importantly, sizeable plots big enough for two-, three-, four- and five-room houses, backyards and, of course, front gardens.³⁴

“GARDEN AREAS”³⁵ AND “GARDENING FACILITIES”:³⁶ THE MAKING OF A GARDEN LOCATION

According to Mayor Thomson the council’s main objective with the new Batho location was, among others, to improve black people’s “everyday conditions

28 *The Friend*, 6.1.1919, p. 4.

29 Thomson was mayor of Bloemfontein from April 1918 to March 1920.

30 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1919–1920, p. 8.

31 *The Friend*, 13.5.1920, p. 6; P. Morris, *A history of black housing in South Africa*, p. 28.

32 J.D. Rheinallt Jones & A.L. Saffery, Social and economic conditions of native life in the Union of South Africa, *Bantu Studies* VII(4), December 1933, pp. 334-335.

33 The plots were leased on a monthly tenancy basis.

34 Du Bruyn, *Batho celebrates a century...*, pp. 3-4; *The Friend*, 13.5.1920, p. 6; *The Friend*, 5.5.1921, p. 5; *The Friend*, 16.11.1928, p. 13.

35 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1919–1920, p. 8.

36 Historical Papers, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg (hereafter HP): AD 1765, Yearly report on locations 1925–1926, p. 2.

of living, housing and cleanliness”.³⁷ There happened to be a direct link between “everyday conditions of living, housing and cleanliness” and the council’s intention to develop “a hygienic Native township”, to quote the segregationist language of that time. In addition to providing a clean living environment, the council also intended to offer tangible benefits in the form of “sanitary healthy houses”.³⁸ The terms “sanitary” and “healthy” not only referred to the quality of the houses but they also implied the beautification of Batho by considering aesthetics and “aesthetic values”.³⁹ Although seemingly well-intentioned, these patronising terms stipulating hygiene and cleanliness were, in fact, directly related to the “sanitation syndrome”.

In order to practically implement the above-mentioned ideals, Thomson explained that Batho’s “sanitary healthy houses” were to be “set in their own plot of ground 50 ft. by 75.”⁴⁰ The council’s blueprint for Batho—the Location Plan⁴¹—stipulated minimum requirements of which the most important was the prescribed size of individual plots. Batho’s plots were indeed larger than the minimum size of 50 by 50 feet prescribed by the national Model Location Regulations⁴² but they were still substantially smaller than the stands in Bloemfontein’s whites-only suburbs, which averaged 50 by 100 feet.⁴³ Although the increased size of Batho’s plots allowed for the building of bigger houses, the primary reason for expanding the size was to allow residents enough space for laying out proper gardens. For this reason, Thomson keenly reported that “garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.”⁴⁴ had been provided for Batho’s residents.⁴⁵

The use of the term “garden areas” instead of the customary “plots” or “stands” indicates the premium that was placed on gardens and gardening. Bloemfontein’s dynamic superintendent of native locations, Mr J.R. Cooper⁴⁶ (1881–1946), a born and bred Englishman, explained that the “larger frontage to the stands” afforded the residents “extended gardening facilities”.⁴⁷ In fact, Cooper—a keen gardener himself—argued that the “frontage” (space for front gardens) afforded to the plots should have been even larger and Batho’s streets narrower. He was also concerned that, in some cases, the position of the houses on the plots compromised the space available for front gardens: “the houses might have been erected deeper in the stands, which would have allowed space for [bigger] front gardens and limited the space for Panthokies [shacks] and the erection of outside rooms.”⁴⁸

Cooper’s concern regarding the space available for gardens related to both practical and aesthetic considerations. Both were equally important, especially if the dynamic relationship that normally exists between a house and the street it faces, and how and where the garden fits into this relationship, is applied to Batho. Since Bloemfontein’s founding, garden design trends among the city’s white residents⁴⁹ had had a major influence on the style and layout of the gardens of Bloemfontein’s black residents. This was even more so in the case of Batho’s gardens, not only because of the processes of acculturation and intercultural influence between the white and black cultures,⁵⁰ but also because most of the garden labourers who maintained the white people’s gardens were black and lived in Batho.⁵¹

37 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1919–1920, p. 6.

38 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1921–1922, p. 13.

39 Consideration to “aesthetics” and “aesthetic values” runs like a golden thread through the archival documents on Batho’s beautification. For more details, see FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1929–1930, p. 14; HP: AD 1765, Annual report of Native Administration Department 1929–1930, p. 2; FSPA: MBL 3/1/21, Mayor’s minute 1930, p. xiv.

40 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1921–1922, p. 13.

41 FSPA: MBL 1/2/4/1/2, Minutes of ordinary meeting of Native Affairs Committee, 18.3.1918, p. 2; *The Friend*, 3.9.1929, p. 9.

42 For complete regulations, see FSPA: MBL 1/2/4/1/6, Location Regulations 1924, pp. 1-8.

43 Approximately 16.5 x 33 metres. *The Friend*, 6.11.1937, p. 14.

44 FSPA: MBL 3/1/19, Mayor’s minute 1919–1920, p. 8.

45 *Ibid.*

46 Cooper was superintendent of locations from 1923 to 1945.

47 HP: AD 1765, Yearly report on locations 1925–1926, p. 2.

48 HP: AD 1765, Yearly report on locations 1926–1927, p. 2.

49 For a detailed discussion of the design and layout of Bloemfontein’s white residents’ gardens during the period 1846 to 1939, see Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, pp. 212-260.

50 W.A. Haviland, *Cultural anthropology*, pp. 426-427; C.J. Maritz, Enkele politieke gevolge en implikasies van die akkulturasieproses vir Suid-Afrika, *Africanus* 6(1 & 2), November 1976, pp. 20-23, 25; G. Cronjé (ed.), *Kultuurbeïnvloeding tussen blankes en bantoe in Suid-Afrika*, pp. 1-9.

51 Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, pp. 399-407.

The influence of Bloemfontein’s white residents’ garden taste on black people’s gardens was particularly evident in the changing relationship between the house and the street during the years between the two World Wars (1918–1939) and the space(s) allowed for the laying out of gardens. Since Bloemfontein’s founding until the end of the 19th century, most white residents’ houses were built right on the street or sidewalk with only a narrow strip left open for a row of trees or rectangular flowerbeds. Most ornamental gardens were laid out behind houses, along with orchards and small vineyards. By the time Batho was established, the relationship between house and street in Bloemfontein had already changed to the point where the ornamental flower garden had moved from the backyard to the front of the house and, in some cases, also the sides of the house.⁵²

Following the trend in Bloemfontein’s white suburbs, the overwhelming majority of Batho’s newly built houses were not positioned right on the street as had been the case historically with the city’s early Dutch-speaking residents.⁵³ Instead, they were placed in a more or less central position on the plot. Consequently, enough space was made available between the house (and its *stoep*⁵⁴) and the street for laying out ornamental front gardens. A small minority of Batho’s residents preferred to have no front flower gardens in order to allow space for bigger backyards and the laying out of vegetable gardens, small orchards and maize (*Zea mays*) patches behind and, in some cases, beside the houses. Following the authentic Dutch custom, some of Batho’s houses were built right on the street. This arrangement allowed just enough space for narrow flowerbeds and often only a clipped hedge or fence-hedge (Fig. 2).⁵⁵

It was, however, not Dutch but English (British) cultural influence which had exerted itself in Bloemfontein and Batho during the inter-War period. This

growing English influence, which may be ascribed to the dominant position occupied by the English-speaking component of Bloemfontein’s population in local decision-making bodies, social structures and in society at large, reinforced the trend towards bigger front gardens. Concerning garden design and layout, the English-speaking residents, who had been strongly influenced by garden design trends in Britain, set the tone. By the time Batho was being established and its gardeners started to make their gardens, Victorian-style cottage gardens had, to a large extent, made way for the structured gardens of the Edwardian period (approximately 1900–1910).⁵⁶ As will be discussed in more detail later, it did not mean that the Victorian style had gone out of fashion completely, at least not in Batho’s gardens. Cottage-style informality was often combined with Edwardian formality to create a unique “hybrid” location garden style characterised by informal planting in formal flowerbeds, clipped hedges, edges and topiary.

The prevalence of historical terms such as “garden area” and “gardening facility” in archival sources often used in conjunction with the terms “plot”, “stand” or “erf” but also as substitutes for these terms, is significant because it underpins the changing relationship between a house and the street it faced. This formal language – popular among municipal officials – indicates, among others, the importance attached to substantial ornamental front gardens as a means of beautification. For example, Cooper stated that through the provisioning of “garden areas” and “gardening facilities”, “every encouragement is given”⁵⁷ by the municipality to convince Batho’s residents of the importance of laying out gardens. In addition to ornamental front gardens, residents were encouraged to lay out vegetable gardens in their backyards. The recommended standard plot size, which extended Batho’s plots lengthwise so that the width of the plots were 50 feet and the length 75

52 S. Botha, *Die verandering en ontwikkeling van die woonhuisargitektuur in Bloemfontein gedurende die tydperk 1846–1946 met bydraende faktore*, unpublished M.A. dissertation, pp. 68–69, 78–80.

53 This practice traces its roots to the Dutch canal cities and towns such as Amsterdam, The Hague, Utrecht and Delft where houses had been traditionally positioned close to the canals (*grachten*). As a result, gardens were laid out not in front of but behind houses. For more information, see H. Zantkuyl, *Stedelijke erven en tuinen tot omstreeks 1850*, in H. Zantkuyl *et al.*, *Erf en tuin in oud-Amsterdam: De ontwikkeling van het besloten erf en de stadstuin in de oude binnenstad*, p. 9.

54 The Afrikaans word *stoep*, also commonly used by English-speaking South Africans, is a vernacular term for a simplified version of a veranda. A *stoep* is typically an uncovered raised platform attached to a house, while a veranda is usually covered and more ornate.

55 Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, p. 308.

56 D. du Bruyn, ‘Township Topiary’: The history of the English-style gardens of Batho, Mangaung (1846–1948), *Navorsing van die Nasionale Museum, Bloemfontein* 27(3), December 2011, pp. 49–50.

57 HP: AD 1765, Yearly report on locations 1925–1926, p. 2.

Figure 2: An original red brick house built right on the street with a fence-hedge in front of it, Thepe Street, Batho, c. late 1930s. The veranda was added later. (Segoe Family Private Photo Collection, Batho: NM Photo Batho 957)

feet, indeed allowed backyard space for the laying out of vegetable gardens, orchards, maize patches and even small vineyards.⁵⁸

While the provisioning of “garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.” might have been considered a significant act of “generosity” by the municipality, it was characterised by a stark anomaly. On the one hand, Batho was envisaged as a model location but, on the other hand, its residents were still subjected to the same racist policies that applied to other black location residents. As members of a dominated and oppressed race group, Batho’s residents had little control over their own lives outside the new location. In fact, they were subjected to stringent social control mechanisms, including a range of permits meant to control the movement of black people to and from the locations. As a result, the “garden areas” were the only spaces over which Batho’s residents had personal control. These “garden areas”, which could never be privately owned, prac-

tically established the parameters of control within the confines of the location.⁵⁹

The council’s idea of “garden areas” and “gardening facilities” extended to spaces other than Batho’s domestic plots since the Location Plan also allowed for open spaces among the plots. These open spaces were developed into public parks and squares, including Mapikela Square and Mogaecho Square – both named after prominent Batho “blockmen” (ward councilors) and community leaders of the inter-War years, namely Thomas Mtobi Mapikela (1869–1945) and John Dixon Mogaecho (?–1937). Another provision made in terms of “garden areas” and “gardening facilities” was the “granting of allotments”⁶⁰ on the outskirts of Batho in order to encourage market-gardening. This development strengthens the argument that gardens and gardening received special consideration in the planning and laying out of Batho as a model location. Importantly, the novel idea of Batho as a future garden suburb – or, more precisely, a garden location – added a significant new dimension to the model location philosophy, namely, the “model-location-as-garden-location”.⁶¹

The concept of “model-location-as-garden-location” raised the bar for model locations elsewhere in the Union and it elevated Batho to becoming a “model” for other similar locations, including Langa (Cape Town),⁶² McNamee Village (Port Elizabeth)⁶³ and Lamontville (Durban).⁶⁴ The same arguments that applied to Batho’s gardens also applied to the gardens of many older South African townships, particularly to those laid out next to towns and cities which boasted substantial English-speaking populations such as the ones mentioned above.⁶⁵ However, the garden location idea should be viewed both in its South African context and in its broader international context. The garden location concept was, to a great extent, inspired by the dominant town

58 *Ibid.*

59 Du Bruyn, ‘Township Topiary’: The history..., pp. 74-75.

60 HP: AD 1765, Yearly report on locations 1925–1926, p. 2.

61 FSPA: MBL 1/2/4/1/16, Report of Superintendent of Locations, June 1929: Annexure A, 4.7.1929, p. 1.

62 N. Coetzer, Langa Township in the 1920s – an (extra)ordinary Garden Suburb, *South African Journal of Art History* 24(1), 2009, pp. 1-19.

63 Maylam, pp. 19-38.

64 L. Torr, Providing for the “better-class native”: The creation of Lamontville, 1923–1933, *South African Geographical Journal* 69(1), 1987, pp. 31-46.

65 D. du Bruyn & M. Oelofse, “The idea of beautifying the surroundings”: Bloemfontein’s (Mangaung) Batho location a “garden location”? (c. 1918–1939), *New Contree* 84, July 2020, pp. 40-41.

planning trend of the Edwardian period, namely the “garden city”⁶⁶ and “garden suburb”⁶⁷ philosophies of the influential British town planning visionary, Ebenezer Howard (1850–1928). The influence of Howard’s philosophies on the garden location idea will subsequently be discussed.

**“HAVING FRESH AIR AND A WIDER
OUTLOOK UPON LIFE”:⁶⁸ THE GARDEN
CITY MOVEMENT’S INFLUENCE ON THE
GARDEN LOCATION IDEA**

Ebenezer Howard’s thoughts and principles influenced town and city planners not only in Britain but also in the British colonies and dominions, including South Africa. Bloemfontein, with its predominantly English-speaking city council, was no exception.⁶⁹ The important point is whether and, if so, to what extent, Howard’s philosophies and, specifically, his idea of the “garden suburb”, also influenced the layout of South African locations such as Batho. The novelty of Howard’s ideas resonated with South African town and city planners, who happened to be mostly Englishmen, many of whom were born and educated in Britain. Consequently, the Garden City Movement, of which Howard was the chief proponent, was particularly influential in South Africa during Batho’s early years, namely the late 1910s and early 1920s.⁷⁰

As a matter of fact, the Movement was so influential in South Africa that many of the Union’s location residents, including readers of the popular *Umteteli wa Bantu*,⁷¹ were familiar with it. In a leading article published in the paper in 1921, the question was raised as to whether the principles of the Movement would also be applied in the Union’s locations as had been the case in some whites-only suburbs of Cape

Town (Pinelands) and Johannesburg (Parktown).⁷² Considering the fact that municipal housing for location dwellers was widely debated among the Union’s black urban residents, including in Bloemfontein, the paper stated that “we [black people] are assuming—and we take it that our assumption is justified—that they [municipal authorities] do not contemplate placing seats in these gardens [public gardens laid out in white garden suburbs] for the Natives upon whose services they are entirely dependent”.⁷³ The paper not only commented on the practice of providing racially segregated public parks for blacks and whites but also wryly suggested to the Union’s “city fathers” that “instead of speaking glowingly of the Movement, whereby the people would grow up in liberty, having fresh air and a wider outlook upon life, would it not be better if they gave their attention to the housing of Natives in municipal areas?”.⁷⁴

As far as Batho’s layout is concerned, the influence of the Garden City Movement and Howard’s philosophies is obvious, whether in the sense of a “garden location” based on the “garden suburb” idea or, at least, a “location with gardens”. The municipality’s insistence on increased plot sizes to accommodate domestic gardens, the provisioning of English-style allotments for market gardens and, importantly, the allocation of open spaces for the laying out of public parks, gardens and squares, reveal the Movement’s influence. Throughout the 1920s and 1930s, the idea of a garden location and the value presumably added to a location by the laying out of domestic and public gardens, remained a guiding principle for Bloemfontein’s municipality.⁷⁵

Towards 1939, when Batho approached the end of its “golden age”, the council’s vision for this location as a garden location had not faded yet. It also seems

-
- 66 E. Howard, *Garden cities of to-morrow*, pp. vi-viii; Anon., What is a Garden City? The example of Letchworth, *The South African Lady’s Pictorial and Home Journal* XI(132), August 1921, p. 29.
- 67 M. Clapson, The suburban aspiration in England since 1919, *Contemporary British History* 14(1), 2000, p. 152.
- 68 *Umteteli wa Bantu*, 5.11.1921, p. 2.
- 69 For Howard’s influence on town planning in Bloemfontein, see FSPA: MBL 1/2/3/1/34, New town hall: Proposed site, 17.1.1929, pp. 4-6.
- 70 Coetzer, pp. 1-2; *The Friend*, 27.6.1922, p. 5; *Die Volksblad*, 19.10.1922, p. 3.
- 71 *Umteteli wa Bantu*, which means “Mouthpiece of the People”, was a weekly newspaper with a predominantly black nationwide readership. It was established in 1920 and discontinued in 1956.
- 72 T.S. Somerville, Our first garden city, *The Outspan* 2(38), 18.11.1927, p. 43; G.M. van der Waal, Aantekeninge oor party voorstede van Johannesburg, *Africana Notes and News* 21(2), June 1974, pp. 64-65.
- 73 *Umteteli wa Bantu*, 5.11.1921, p. 2.
- 74 *Ibid.*
- 75 L.N. Melao, *Guidelines that determine low-income housing plot sizes and layout: A case study of Maphikela (Batho Location) and Bloemanda in the Mangaung residential area*, unpublished M.A. dissertation, pp. 22-23, 51-79.

as though the majority of Bloemfontein's white residents supported such a vision for Batho since the idea of Bloemfontein as the "Union's Garden City"⁷⁶ did much to improve the city's image and status in the eyes of the Union's larger cities such as Johannesburg, Cape Town and Durban. Those among Bloemfontein's white residents who concerned themselves with location matters were generally in favour of the concept of the "great native location" as an idealised future black location characterised by "ample open spaces" and "large, gardened areas".⁷⁷ It was argued that the creation of such a location, that is, a garden location, would ultimately have been to the advantage of not only Bloemfontein's black residents but, seen from a health perspective, also its white residents. In terms of "sanitation syndrome" thinking, a garden location was also considered a "sanitary" location that posed a reduced threat to white people's health. From the council's point of view, Batho exemplified the "great native location" because it was "sanitary" but, above all, because of its gardens.⁷⁸

**"LITTLE ORCHARDS AND GARDENS
SURROUND THE HOUSES"⁷⁹
IMPRESSIONS, DESCRIPTIONS
AND RECOLLECTIONS OF BATHO'S
ORNAMENTAL GARDENS**

One of the earliest descriptions of the gardens that were laid out on Batho's "garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft." dates back to 1922, when Emilie J. Solomon, a Capetonian who attended a labour union convention in Bloemfontein, visited Batho at the invitation of the mayor, Mr W.M. Barnes.⁸⁰ In an article, which she had written originally for *The Cape Times* and which had been published in *Umteteli wa Bantu*, she gave detailed descriptions of Batho's gardens. Solomon wrote that she and other delegates saw "little orchards and gardens surround the houses" in a location "well laid out with broad streets".⁸¹ She also noticed "much healthy competition in building and gardening",⁸² a significant observation that must be viewed against

the backdrop of the relative economic progress made by Bloemfontein's black residents during the 1920s. As a result, a sizeable class of "educated and advanced natives"⁸³ such as Mapikela and Mogaecho emerged and became emblematic of Batho's "golden age".

Bloemfontein's class of literate and semi-literate black people made up the bulk of Batho's residents. They included tradespeople (tailors, dressmakers, shoemakers, masons, blacksmiths and carpenters), semi-professionals (shop assistants, chefs, waiters, clerks, messengers, interpreters and other low-ranking civil servants) and professionals (nurses and teachers), and because of their improved economic position, they were able to spend more on their houses and yards. Consequently, an increasingly visible class distinction began to develop between this group and the so-called "unsophisticated types",⁸⁴ namely those who were either unemployed or who had to make a living as low-paid domestic servants, manual labourers and garden labourers working for Bloemfontein's whites. Cooper considered this socio-economic trend as significant, especially the financially able group's ability to contribute to Batho's beautification, ultimately turning it into a class-differentiated garden location. He argued that this group's "laying out of flower and vegetable gardens is an indication of a class distinction as pronounced among the natives as among the Europeans."⁸⁵

In 1934, a local black court interpreter, John Mancoe, published a comprehensive guide on Bloemfontein's black and coloured residents. The *First Edition of the Bloemfontein Bantu and Coloured People's Directory* contained information on the social lives of the location residents and was written by a black person from the perspective of the location residents, specifically those who lived in Batho. Based on Mancoe's descriptions of Batho's man-made landscape, it is argued that despite the economic depression of the late 1920s and early 1930s, an influential black middle-

76 "The Vagabond" (pseudonym), Union's garden city: Beauty spots in the Free State capital, *The Friend*, 16.4.1927, p. 11.

77 "Old Bloemfonteiner" (pseudonym), When Bloemfontein's population is 250,000: Town-planning for the future, *The Friend*, 5.10.1936, p. 8.

78 *Ibid.*

79 E.J. Solomon, Bloemfontein Native Location, *Umteteli wa Bantu*, 19.8.1922, p. 3.

80 Barnes was mayor of Bloemfontein from April 1922 to March 1923.

81 Solomon, p. 3.

82 *Ibid.*

83 HP: AD 1765, Annual report of Native Administration Department 1931–1932, p. 2.

84 *Ibid.*, p. 3.

85 *Ibid.* See also HP: AD 1765, Report on locations 1936, p. 3.

class had established itself there. The preferred status symbols of this economic class included a house with a *stoep* and, importantly, a well laid-out garden.⁸⁶ Some noteworthy private houses and gardens listed in Mancoe’s directory deserve mentioning, including the house and garden that belonged to the blockman, John Dixon Mogaecho and his wife, Emily. The Mogaechos’ residence was singled out for its impressive “front verandah and cemented stoep”⁸⁷ (Fig. 3). As had been the case with the Mogaechos’ house, *stoeps* served an important practical purpose in Batho and should be considered in direct relation to ornamental front gardens.

Figure 3: John Dixon and Emily Mogaecho’s son, Eric, at the garden gate that led to the house’s veranda and front door, Choane Street, Batho, c. late 1950s. The house was built during the late 1920s. Note the garden gate and garden arch. (Mogaecho Family Private Photo Collection, Batho: NM Photo Batho 622)

Due to the modest size of their houses, most of Batho’s house owners had to integrate their front gardens and outdoor spaces around their houses into their indoor living spaces. This practice was, of course, not unique to Batho. The same phenomenon was also noticeable in the domestic environments of black people elsewhere, for example, in the 18th and 19th century slave yards in the American South where yards functioned as “extensions of the house”.⁸⁸ Batho residents, including the Mogaechos, socialised in the

open air, most often on the sidewalks, and preferred to live around their houses, especially during the hot summer months. Furthermore, extended families were big; therefore, they had to create additional outdoor living areas in order to maximise the available indoor space. No matter how small, *stoeps* provided this much-needed living space. For Batho residents *stoeps* also functioned as both transitional and living spaces: On the one hand, the *stoep* served as a transitional space between the house and front garden, while on the other, it became an extension of the house and functioned as an additional room. The addition of tall-clipped hedges and green “walls” further extended the outside living spaces by creating outdoor “rooms” (Fig. 4).⁸⁹

Figure 4: Clipped privet hedges create a green enclosure attached to a house in Makgothi Street, Batho, 2011. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 171)

Apart from its veranda, the Mogaechos’ house was also known for its attractive ornamental front garden that was laid out during the late 1920s. Emily Mogaecho hailed from a family to whom gardening was “an in-bred thing”,⁹⁰ to quote her sister, Pinky Mokgele (born 1928). According to the Mogaechos’ grandson, Mogrey Mogaecho (born 1969), his grandparents’ garden was a typical English-style garden known for its flower varieties, including oleanders (*Nerium oleander*) and roses (*Rosa* spp.). Mogrey,

86 J. Mancoe, *First edition of the Bloemfontein Bantu and Coloured people’s directory, passim*; K. Schoeman, *Bloemfontein: Die ontstaan van ’n stad, 1846–1946*, pp. 286–288; C. Shannon, *Library & community hall at Batho. The mental image: Identity & orientation*, unpublished M.Arch. dissertation, p. 15.

87 Mancoe, p. 54.

88 Heath & Bennett, p. 43. See also p. 38.

89 Schoeman, p. 287; D.C. Ras & I. Coetzee, *’n Ondersoek na die administrasie en grondgebruik in laerinkomstegebiede, met spesifieke verwysing na die effek van die amalgamasie van plaaslike owerhede daarop*, unpublished M.A. dissertation, p. 130; Shannon, p. 15.

90 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with P. Mokgele, Bochabela, 16.6.2013.

who cherished fond memories of the garden and maintained it the way his grandmother did, remembered that the single outstanding element was the impeccably clipped privet (*Ligustrum* spp.) hedge or fence-hedge, which spanned the entire length of the property facing the street. Planted on the inside of a wire netting fence, the hedge screened the veranda from the street in order to secure privacy for the family.⁹¹

“Our hedges was [sic] famous”⁹² Mogrey remembered, referring not only to the clipped hedges in his grandparents’ garden but also to clipped hedges in other Batho gardens, thereby confirming the strong influence that these formal front hedges had exerted on Batho’s garden landscape. It appears as though gardening had been “an in-bred thing” not only for Emily but for many other Batho home owners as well, since attractive gardens were in no short supply during the 1920s and 1930s. One of the best-known gardens belonged to the health inspector for the locations, Temba Msikinya. According to Mancoe, Msikinya’s house was complemented by a “nicely-planned garden”.⁹³ Not far from Msikinya’s garden stood one of the location’s landmarks, namely the double-story house of Thomas Mapikela. This house, with its two verandas, was built “according to modern tastes”⁹⁴ and complemented by a handsome garden that, according to the popular taste, was enclosed by a clipped hedge. When the Mapikela garden was laid out in the 1920s, the most popular hedging plants were privet, specifically *Ligustrum vulgare* and *Ligustrum lucidum*, as well as cypress (*Cupressus* spp.).⁹⁵

The gardens mentioned in Mancoe’s directory were, of course, not the only attractive gardens in Batho during its early years. According to information obtained through oral history interviews conducted by the author with 57 Batho residents during the period

2008–2016,⁹⁶ ornamental gardens abounded in the garden location in the 1920s and 1930s. “Batho was a beautiful location in those days – it was green and there were many beautiful gardens everywhere”⁹⁷ remembered Sarah M. Mahabane (born 1927). Of all Batho’s gardens, she had the clearest memories of the ornamental flower garden made by her late father, Malachi Seleka, at the family’s home in Lovedale Road. Seleka, who worked as a gardener and groundskeeper at Grey College in town, “did not mind to come home and also be a gardener there.”⁹⁸ Seleka was very fond of hollyhocks (*Alcea rosea*) and dahlias (*Dahlia pinnata*) – two types of flowers that were popular among Batho’s gardeners during the 1920s and 1930s. According to Mahabane, the Selekas’ vegetable garden was situated behind the house as was the case with most vegetable gardens in Batho. Most of all, Mahabane remembered the clipped hedge in front of her parents’ garden. Maintained by her father, the razor-sharp privet hedge was not very high: “you could see over it”,⁹⁹ Mahabane recalled.

Another long-time Batho resident, Joy M. Direko (born 1944), vividly recalled the stories her parents, Michael and Nancy Mochochoko, told her about Batho’s gardens. Both her parents were teachers, and her father was the principal of Mangaung Primary School in Batho’s Fort Hare Road. During the 1920s and 1930s, black learners in the lower grades of primary school had to take vocational subjects, including Gardening and Nature Study. Extensive flower and vegetable gardens were laid out on the school premises, and the Mochochokos’ garden, which had been laid out in 1935, benefited from the school gardens. Direko explained: “My mother’s garden was an ‘extension’ of the school gardens because the plants in her garden were leftovers from the school gardens.”¹⁰⁰ The Mochochokos’ garden included a formal, ornamental front garden with rectangular

91 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with M. Mogaecho, Batho, 9.4.2013; D. du Bruyn, The story of a township garden: Mogrey’s family recollections, *Culna* 68, November 2013, pp. 34-35.

92 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with M. Mogaecho, Batho, 9.4.2013.

93 Mancoe, p. 53.

94 *Ibid.*, p. 55.

95 C. Twala, “Ulundi-Kaya”: The dwelling of Thomas Mtobi Mapikela in Bloemfontein (Mangaung) – its historical significance, *South African Journal of Cultural History* 18(1), June 2004, pp. 63-67; D. du Bruyn, Oral testimonies as a source of community history, with special reference to the Batho Project, Bloemfontein, *South African Journal of Cultural History* 24(2), November 2010, pp. 9-10.

96 Of the total of 57 gardeners who were interviewed, 29 were male and 28 female.

97 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with S.M. Mahabane, Batho, 7 & 20.11.2014.

98 *Ibid.*

99 *Ibid.*

100 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with J.M. Direko, Batho, 11.11.2014.

flowerbeds containing, among others, hollyhocks, dahlias and roses.¹⁰¹

While attractive front flower gardens had certainly been the norm in Batho during the 1920s and 1930s, not all of Batho’s gardens were memorable as a result of their flowers. Some gardens were remembered for their topiary and the way in which it defined those gardens. Most interviewees closely linked topiary and formality. Moreover, they associated the concept of formality automatically with the clipping and pruning of plants. Herbert Rampana (born 1957) was candid about the fact that he had found inspiration for his own garden from a portrait of a formal European garden that he displayed in his Batho home. Like many other Batho gardeners, Rampana expressed a personal fondness for the straight lines and round shapes according to which the plants in the picture were clipped. He explained how he aimed to replicate the crisp and dense look of the topiary depicted in the portrait in his own garden: “I cut them [shrubs] so that they must come together”.¹⁰² Another Batho gardener, Eugenia Ngatane (born 1969), explained that to Batho’s gardeners the clipping of plants into topiary is “a way of pruning so that they [plants] can’t grow bigger than they were supposed to”.¹⁰³ Ngatane argued that certain plants were not meant to grow big and by clipping them she gave them “a better shape”.¹⁰⁴ Simon Ditema (born 1960), an entrepreneur who sold plants from home, reasoned that a gardener should not only focus on individual plants but should also consider the big picture. He viewed the clipping of plants into topiary ultimately as a “way of shaping your garden”.¹⁰⁵

Other Batho gardens were remembered specifically for their clipped hedges, and often for their hedges only. One such garden belonged to the Sebegoe family (Fig. 2), who lived next door to the Mochochokos. The Sebegoes’ granddaughter,

Florence K. Segoe (born 1940), explained that the house had been built by her husband, Jacob Segoe’s grandfather, during the late 1930s. The house was situated on the street with only a small space between the sidewalk and the house’s veranda. Behind the Sebegoes’ house was a big backyard with a huge vine arbour. This typical Dutch-style layout allowed room for only a clipped hedge and, in some cases, narrow flowerbeds. In the Sebegoes’ case, there were both but it was the beautiful clipped privet hedge that happened to be the main feature.¹⁰⁶ According to Florence, the hedge in question was planted by the Sebegoes’ son-in-law, Peter Segoe (Jacob’s father), who lived with his wife, Nellie (née Sebegoe), and her parents. Florence recalled that the hedge had always been clipped “the same way my father-in-law clipped it”,¹⁰⁷ namely a rectangular shape with a flat surface. In fact, the hedge’s shape had become a family tradition.¹⁰⁸ It seems as if this shape had become traditional for many Batho gardeners because of their shared preference for straight lines and sharp corners. Concerning the hedge in her front garden, Keabecoe Zim (born 1962) was adamant about its preferred shape: “I like the square shape very much”.¹⁰⁹ In a similar vein, R.P. Moilola (born 1947) insisted that his hedge “must be square”,¹¹⁰ while Abednego Loape, a fourth generation Batho gardener born in 1983, expressed his preference as follows: “the lines must be straight – I like it that way”.¹¹¹ These Batho gardeners’ stylistic preferences point to a taste for a specific garden style that will be the subject of discussion in the next section.

“A FORMAL LAYOUT WITH STONE EDGES”:¹¹² SEMI-VERNACULAR ENGLISH-STYLE, FORMALITY, AND TOPIARY IN BATHO’S ORNAMENTAL GARDENS

101 *Ibid.*

102 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with H.T. Rampana, Batho, 28.3.2013.

103 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with E.M. Nagatane, Batho, 29.10.2014.

104 *Ibid.*

105 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with S.P. Ditema, Batho, 8.5.2013.

106 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with F.K. Segoe, Batho, 4.11.2014.

107 *Ibid.*

108 D. du Bruyn, A garden is not a garden without a hedge: The story of the Segoe family’s Batho garden, *Culna* 70, November 2015, pp. 11-13.

109 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with K.M. Zim, Batho, 28.10.2014.

110 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with R.P. Moilola, Batho, 30.3.2011.

111 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with A.K. Loape, Batho, 5.4.2011.

112 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with J.M. Direko, Batho, 11.11.2014.

Apart from the fact that all the previously mentioned ornamental gardens were originally laid out on Batho's "garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.", they had something else in common: They may be described as semi-vernacular or "hybrid" and, as such, most of them shared three key characteristics. Firstly, because Batho's gardens were the products of acculturation and intercultural influence, they displayed a blend of patrician (European/British) and vernacular (African) influences. For the purpose of this article, the terms "semi-vernacular" and "hybrid" essentially refer to a garden that appeared to be English because it contained typical English elements. At the same time, however, it was adapted to local conditions and displayed African influences. Secondly, Batho's gardens displayed a predominantly formal and regimented layout and thirdly, they contained topiary in the form of clipped hedges, edges and other shapes, which served either a functional or an aesthetic purpose, or both.

Concerning the first characteristic, it must be emphasised that the English gardening trends and styles that had been influencing Bloemfontein's gardens since 1846 still predominated when Batho was founded. As a result, English influence became increasingly visible in the style and layout of Batho's gardens. While the influence of the English cottage-garden style¹¹³ was still popular in white-owned gardens, Batho's gardens had become more structured and formal. As it had been the case with Batho's houses, the Edwardian style,¹¹⁴ with its preference for simplified formality and sound proportions, also seems to have influenced Batho's ornamental gardens.¹¹⁵ The basic design of the houses built in Batho during the 1920s and 1930s was often based on the classic axial principle, which meant that the front door and passage were aligned with the back door. Typically, this arrangement reinforced the occurrence of what may be described as a simple formal axial garden. This garden style, which has its roots in the late Medieval

Agnes and early Renaissance,¹¹⁶ refers to a formal framework in which an equal number of square or rectangular flowerbeds with narrow paths in-between were aligned to either the north-south axis or the east-west axis, or both. Batho's version of an Edwardian garden and a classic simple formal axial garden are strikingly similar.¹¹⁷

In Batho's ornamental gardens, the customary garden path was usually aligned with the centrally positioned front door. This layout automatically created a formal front garden consisting of two symmetrical sections separated by a straight garden path. Inside the two sections, the flowerbeds were usually rectangular, square or circular. Inside the flowerbeds, the planting was either formal, that is, in rows, or informal, that is to say in the random fashion of English cottage-style planting. While the basic design of Batho's gardens was simplified Edwardian, the planting was often of a cottage-style nature, as still happens to be the case in many gardens today (Fig. 5). Importantly, though, these English styles found expression within an African context. This trend is comparable to the way in which British colonists have influenced the appearance of traditional African vernacular gardens in former British colonies such as the Gold Coast (Ghana), British East Africa (Kenya), Tanganyika (Tanzania), Northern Rhodesia (Zambia) and Southern Rhodesia (Zimbabwe) during the 19th and 20th centuries. Due to these foreign influences, a semi-vernacular or "hybrid" garden, which featured a predominantly formal layout with flowers, clipped hedges and topiary, had evolved in colonial Africa.¹¹⁸ Batho's gardens display characteristics that are comparable to black gardens in the afore-mentioned former British colonies. At the same time, however, Batho's gardens differ from black people's gardens in other parts of the world, notably in the USA. For example, research conducted during the 1970s by Gene Wilhelm among African-American gardeners in Brushy, Texas, revealed mostly informal garden layouts with no or very few examples of clipped hedges and topiary.¹¹⁹

113 For a discussion of the influence of the English cottage-garden style on Bloemfontein's gardens, see Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, pp. 223-238.

114 For a discussion of the influence of the Arts and Crafts and Edwardian garden styles on Bloemfontein's gardens, see Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, pp. 240-253.

115 Du Bruyn, 'Township Topiary': The history..., pp. 49-50; D.A. van der Bank, Eduardiane invloede in die Oranjerivierkolonie, *South African Journal of Cultural History* 10(1), May 1996, pp. 60, 65, 73.

116 A. Huxley, *An illustrated history of gardening*, p. 26.

117 Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, p. 438; Du Bruyn, 'Township Topiary': The history..., pp. 68-70.

118 For more information on European and British colonial influences on the African vernacular garden, see G. Jellicoe *et al.* (eds), *The Oxford companion to gardens*, pp. 3, 155-159, 277-279; G. van Zuylen, *The garden: Visions of paradise*, pp. 23-26.

119 G. Wilhelm, Dooryard gardens and gardening in the black community of Brushy, Texas, *Geographical Review* 65(1), January 1975, pp. 73-92.

Figure 5: Cottage-style planting in a Batho garden enclosed by a tall-clipped privet hedge, Makgothi Street, Batho, 2011. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 211)

Figure 6: Overlapping brick edges and iron stones (in the background) indicate the original layout of the garden in front of Mangaung Primary School, Fort Hare Road, Batho, 2012. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 477)

The “hybrid” English garden which had evolved in Bloemfontein’s white suburbs since 1846¹²⁰ is also applicable to Batho in the sense that Batho’s English-style gardens also appeared to be “English”. Owing to the influence of acculturation and intercultural influence, typical English garden elements had found their way into Batho’s gardens, including flowerbeds edged with overlapping bricks (Fig. 6) and fashionable decorative elements such as metal garden arches and garden gates. At the same time, however, Batho’s gardens contained elements that rooted them in the local context, that is, the local natural and man-made environment as well as the climate. These elements included, among others, a variety of indigenous shrubs and trees, as well as flowerbeds edged with local blue stones and/or iron stones¹²¹ (Fig. 6).

While Waaihoek’s gardens came about in a rather haphazard and unplanned fashion, Batho’s gardens were generally better conceived, better planned and better laid out. In many cases, the same care that went into planning the houses also went into the gardens, a trend that may be ascribed to English cultural influence. The one important English element that defined Batho’s gardens was the prevalence of topiary, specifically clipped hedges of various heights, which enclosed gardens and yards. This quintessential

feature of the traditional English (and Dutch) garden was transferred from the gardens of Bloemfontein’s white residents to Batho’s gardens by the black and coloured garden labourers who were responsible for maintaining the white people’s topiary. The age-old concept of a garden as a hedged-in or fenced-in entity¹²² appeared to have become characteristic of the semi-vernacular or “hybrid” location garden in general and Batho’s topiary gardens in particular. During the 1920s and 1930s, a garden and yard without a hedge or, at least, a fence around it was considered undesirable. Importantly, topiary—whether in the form of a clipped edge, hedge or standard (“lollipop”-shaped) tree or shrub—was the patrician element that influenced the style of Batho’s gardens and essentially defined their semi-vernacular or “hybrid” character¹²³ (Fig. 7).

Another characteristic English element which featured prominently in Batho’s gardens was the choice of plants and flowers. Typical “English” flowering plants such as hollyhocks, foxgloves (*Digitalis purpurea*), dahlias, lavender (*Lavandula* spp.) and roses proliferated in gardens. The preference for “English” plants and flowers was particularly evident in the garden laid out by the Mogaechos. According to Mogrey the story of his grandparents’ ornamental garden began in the late 1920s when the couple laid

120 For a discussion of the historical development of the “hybrid” English garden in Bloemfontein’s white suburbs since 1846, see Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, pp. 235-238.

121 Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, p. 438; Du Bruyn, ‘Township Topiary’: The history..., pp. 68-70.

122 The garden as an enclosed and bounded piece of land or space is a crucial aspect of pre-World War II domestic gardens. For more information, see A. van Erp-Houtepen, The etymological origin of the garden, *Journal of Garden History* 6(3), 1986, p. 227.

123 Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and...*, pp. 438-439; Du Bruyn, ‘Township Topiary’: The history..., pp. 68-70.

Figure 7: A typical English-style semi-vernacular or “hybrid” topiary garden with a simple formal axial layout, Moiloa Street, Batho, 2009. Note the ivy-covered arch and wire netting fence. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 80)

out a rather small front garden to complement their veranda house. The Mogaechos’ garden displayed the mentioned characteristics of a typical English-style garden, complete with clipped hedges and a garden arch over the garden gate (Fig. 3). According to Mogrey, English influence on his grandmother (Emily) became notably strong after she befriended white English-speaking women in Bloemfontein. Through them Emily developed a fondness not only for English gardens in general but also for old-fashioned “English” roses.¹²⁴

Concerning the second key characteristic that Batho’s gardens had in common, namely a predominantly formal layout, research findings are based on oral testimonies and tangible evidence provided by remnants of original garden layouts found on a number of Batho plots. One of the interviewees, Sarah Mahabane, reported that in the case of her parents’ garden, both the flower and vegetable beds were rectangular in shape. “My mother liked straight lines”¹²⁵ Mahabane remembered and, according to her, this preference resulted in a regimented and formal garden layout. The same trend was visible in the gardens of Batho’s public buildings such as schools and churches. Although these gardens are

beyond the scope of this article, an example worth mentioning is the garden that was made in front of the Mangaung Primary School in Batho, where Joy Direko’s parents were teachers. According to Joy, the garden “had a formal layout with stone edges around the flowerbeds”¹²⁶ (Fig. 6). This garden provided the plants for Joy’s parents’ garden and also inspired its formal layout.

Tangible evidence also provided design clues and, in some cases, a number of Batho’s existing historical gardens still reflect the original layout or design blueprint such as the afore-mentioned school’s front garden (Fig. 6). In other cases, the original garden had vanished completely, but remnants of former brick-edged flowerbeds and the original boundaries of the garden reveal the basic outline of the authentic design, which is usually a simple formal axial layout. In this study, the focus was not on tangible remnants of below-ground features, which falls within the sub-discipline of garden archaeology¹²⁷ but on the above-ground features. Brick and stone edges, garden paths, terrace retaining walls, steps, irrigation channels, drains, wells, metal water tubs, old standpipes with taps and decorative masonry were found useful as pieces of physical evidence to visually reconstruct the original layout of some of Batho’s gardens.

Finally, regarding the third characteristic, namely topiary, sources such as historical photographs (Figs 2 & 3), living remnants of privet hedges planted during the 1920s and 1930s¹²⁸ and oral testimonies indicate the presence of topiary, particularly clipped hedges and edges, in Batho’s early ornamental gardens. Since the laying out of gardens in Batho commenced in all earnest, the municipality encouraged gardeners to enclose or fence-in their gardens by means of wire netting or alternative fences of an approved type, which included living hedges. In 1920, the city council approved an amount of £120 for “the purpose of fencing the gardens and grounds of the Locations”¹²⁹ in order to prevent gardens, including

124 Du Bruyn, ‘Township Topiary’: The history..., pp. 68-70; National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with M. Mogaecho, Batho, 9.4.2013; P. Mokgele, Bochabela, 16.6.2013; Du Bruyn, The story of a..., pp. 34-35; J. du Plessis, *A history of Christian missions in South Africa*, pp. 454-459.

125 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with S.M. Mahabane, Batho, 7 & 20.11.2014.

126 National Museum Oral History Collection: Interview conducted by D. du Bruyn with J.M. Direko, Batho, 11.11.2014.

127 For information, see K.L. Gleason, To bound and to cultivate: An introduction to the archaeology of gardens and fields, in N.F. Miller & K.L. Gleason (eds), *The archaeology of garden and field*, pp. 1-24; C. Currie, *Garden archaeology: A handbook*, pp. 5-6, 27-32, 147; D. Jacques, The progress of garden archaeology, *The Journal of Garden History* 17(1), 1997, pp. 3-10.

128 Well-maintained privet hedges may survive for up to a century and longer. Personal communication: Dr P.C. Zietsman, Botany Department, National Museum, Bloemfontein, 25.7.2017.

129 *The Friend*, 25.8.1920, p. 7.

allotment gardens, from being damaged by stray animals. Initially, many gardeners opted for wire fences because fencing material was still affordable. During the 1930s, especially after the economic depression of 1929–1933, wire became costly and, as a result, many Batho gardeners opted for a more affordable alternative, namely clipped hedges. On its part, the council argued that the absence of “fencing of a durable and attractive type, has a depressing effect both materially and aesthetically”¹³⁰ on its efforts to beautify Batho and turn it into a garden location. To the council’s delight, the planting of hedges as a more attractive means of enclosing Batho’s plots than wire netting had increased manifold, primarily for economic reasons. Consequently, many of Batho’s “garden areas” became enclosed with neat clipped hedges.¹³¹

As is still the case in Batho today, clipped hedges not only served as a boundary between adjacent plots but also between the sidewalk and the street (public space) and the front garden and stoep (semi-private space; Fig. 8) during the 1920s and 1930s. Since the hedge was often perforated by either a centrally located garden gate (Fig. 8) or a side gate, or both, the hedge functioned as a threshold between the public space on the one hand and the semi-private spaces (garden, stoep and backyard) and private space (house) on the other.¹³² The practical function of Batho’s hedges should also be considered in relation to the fact that during Batho’s early years, the residents’ houses and gardens were surrounded by mostly bare veld.¹³³ By laying out gardens and, most importantly, by planting hedges to enclose their gardens, Batho’s residents strove towards creating intimacy and a sense of security amid the vast expanse of the adjacent open veld. Once again, the ancient concept of the garden as an enclosed entity is applicable. However, despite the importance of the clipped hedge as both a threshold and an element which created intimacy, the fact that Batho’s residents spent most of their social lives outside their houses and street life was part of daily social interaction, must also be taken into account. Thus, the need for security and intimacy was balanced with the need for social interaction and interface with street life, as is still the case today.¹³⁴

Figure 8: A clipped privet hedge perforated by a garden gate serves as a boundary between the sidewalk and street and the front garden and veranda, Makgothi Street, Batho, 2011. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 210)

While clipped hedges and edges of various heights and widths comprised a substantial percentage of Batho’s topiary, they were by no means the only types of clipped garden art that featured in Batho’s ornamental gardens. In fact, most of the styles and types of classic English-style topiary were seen in Batho’s gardens. Over time, as Batho’s topiarists became more skilled in the art of clipping, cutting and pruning, and developed more self-confidence as a result, their topiary creations became inventive and adapted to local conditions. Essentially, Batho’s gardeners took a classic European garden art and indigenised it or, to be more specific, Africanised it. After more than a century of gardening and topiary-making, generations of Batho gardeners have developed their own topiary style which may be described as “township topiary”. “Township topiary” is either characterised by simplicity, that is, simplified and scaled-down renditions of English-style topiary, or originality, that is, inventive and creative versions of classic topiary styles.¹³⁵

Stylistically, “township topiary” results from a combination of the Batho topiarists’ personal preference, creativity, clipping skills and the domestic environment. The types of “township topiary” range

130 FSPA: MBL 3/1/28, Mayor’s minute 1937, p. 17.

131 *Ibid.*

132 FSPA: MBL 1/2/4/1/27, Minutes of ordinary meeting of Native Advisory Board, 6.7.1936, pp. 1-2.

133 An Afrikaans word describing indigenous grassland mostly devoid of trees.

134 A. Nauta, *Waaihoek community museum: Reconstructing the lost narrative*, unpublished M.Arch. dissertation, pp. 75, 77; Schoeman, p. 287.

135 D. du Bruyn, Township topiary – the African way, *Topiarius* 23, Summer 2019, pp. 37-40.

Figure 9: Low-clipped privet hedges define the formal layout of this topiary garden, Khumalo Street, Batho, 2011. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 162)

Figure 11: A privet hedge clipped to resemble cloud formations, Masenya Street, Batho, 2011. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 195)

Figure 10: A freshly-clipped privet block-and-plane, Dilape Street, Batho, 2011. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 236)

Figure 12: A clipped privet fence-hedge adorned with "lollipops", Sesing Street, Batho, 2010. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 132)

from edges or dwarf hedges (Fig. 9), hedges (Fig. 8), fence-hedges (Fig. 2) and green "walls" (Fig. 4) to an extensive variety of shapes, including bonsai-like standards, spheres and domes, "cake stands" and other tiered shapes, block-and-planes (Fig. 10), arches and free-form creations such as figures, animals and other depictions, for instance, cloud formations (Fig. 11). A noteworthy type of "township topiary" that had evolved in Batho's gardens over time is the combination of hedges and shapes, for example, "lollipops" placed on top of a hedge in order to make it both functional and decorative (Fig. 12).

One of the important side effects of the Bloemfontein city council's efforts to turn Batho into a garden location and to develop a gardening cul-

ture among the residents, was the evolution of "township topiary" as a tangible expression of a unique garden identity. The "garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft." did not only provide Batho's gardeners with spaces for laying out gardens but also with opportunities for creative expression. It is argued that they derived a sense of identity from expressing themselves through their clipped art. As topiary became more established, this practice became entrenched in the Batho gardeners' cultural identity. The hypothesis of French sociologist, Michel Conan, that dominated and oppressed groups "tend to stick to traditional gardens",¹³⁶ is applicable to Batho's gardeners. However, not only did they adhere to the traditional; they also made it their own.

Finally, it is argued that the Batho gardeners’ topiary creations, of which only a selection was discussed above, brought a unique character to Batho’s ornamental front gardens. There is no doubt that these gardens contributed hugely to Batho becoming a garden location, particularly the type of garden location the municipality had envisaged. After more than a century of clipping, cutting and pruning, topiary still defines Batho’s “garden areas”.¹³⁷

CONCLUSION

In this article, it is argued that the Bloemfontein municipality’s decision to provide the residents of the new Batho location with “garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.” was motivated by a number of reasons, most of which were of a political nature and rooted in the Union government’s segregationist ideology. An important reason was the city council’s desire to turn Batho into the Union’s prime model location and, ultimately, into a garden location. The quality which set the new Batho location apart from most other locations in the Union was the emphasis on aesthetics and the tangible efforts made by both the council and residents to beautify Batho. The council set the stage by providing the residents with “generous” plots in the form of what was described as “garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.” The allocation of these “garden areas” encouraged and enabled residents to lay out ornamental front gardens as well as vegetable gardens in their backyards. The front gardens resembled the English-style gardens that were popular among Bloemfontein’s white residents during the 1920s and 1930s. Most of Batho’s gardens

displayed a predominantly simple formal axial layout enclosed by clipped hedges and often adorned with topiary. A fondness of topiary prompted Batho’s gardeners to create hedges, edges and a great variety of other topiary styles which had gradually evolved into a style of topiary described as “township topiary”. “Township topiary” is considered the tangible expression of a unique garden identity that evolved among Batho’s gardeners over time.

Due to the processes of acculturation and intercultural influence, which involved the Dutch, British and African cultures, Batho’s gardens are described as semi-vernacular or “hybrid”. This description is applicable to Batho’s historical and present gardens. While most gardens display an unmistakable English cottage-garden style, a decidedly African accent is also visible. In most cases, the English and African attributes are superimposed onto a simple formal axial blueprint. Batho’s semi-vernacular or “hybrid” gardens and their history should be seen in their proper historical context. Therefore, it is argued that a better understanding of particular local garden histories such as Batho’s, also illuminates the larger issues of colonialism, racial oppression, segregation, acculturation and intercultural influence. This understanding is only possible through research that draws on historical records and on oral testimonies. Only then will it be possible to write garden histories that, to quote garden historian, John Dixon Hunt, “move from cultural contexts and intellectual climates to real gardens and actual gardeners”.¹³⁸ The story of Batho’s ornamental front gardens that were laid out on “garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.” aims to do just that.

137 Du Bruyn, ‘Township Topiary’: The history, pp. 68-73. For a detailed discussion of the different styles and types of “township topiary”, see Du Bruyn, *Gardens, gardening culture and*, pp. 462-469.

138 J.D. Hunt, Afterword, in E. de Jong, *Nature and art: Dutch garden and landscape architecture, 1650–1740*, p. 157.

REFERENCES

- I Archival Sources
- FREE STATE PROVINCIAL ARCHIVES (FSPA), BLOEMFONTEIN
- UNPUBLISHED MATERIAL
- Municipality of Bloemfontein (MBL):
- Mayor's Minutes
- MBL 3/1/19, Mayor's minute 1919–1920.
- MBL 3/1/19, Mayor's minute 1921–1922.
- MBL 3/1/19, Mayor's minute 1926–1927.
- MBL 3/1/19, Mayor's minute 1929–1930.
- MBL 3/1/21, Mayor's minute 1930.
- MBL 3/1/28, Mayor's minute 1937.
- Native Advisory Board & Native Affairs Committee: Minutes
- MBL 1/2/4/1/2, Minutes of ordinary meeting of Native Affairs Committee, 18.3.1918.
- MBL 1/2/4/1/27, Minutes of ordinary meeting of Native Advisory Board, 6.7.1936.
- Regulations
- MBL 1/2/4/1/6, Location Regulations 1924.
- Reports
- MBL 1/2/4/1/16, Report of Superintendent of Locations, June 1929: Annexure A, 4.7.1929.
- Miscellaneous
- MBL 1/2/3/1/34, New town hall: Proposed site, 17.1.1929.
- Other:
- Manuscripts
- A. 3(4/1) (9/2/2), Extracts: South African Races Committee: Land tenure.
- UNIVERSITY OF THE WITWATERSRAND, HISTORICAL PAPERS (HP), JOHANNESBURG
- UNPUBLISHED MATERIAL
- Municipality of Bloemfontein:
- Reports
- AD 1765, Yearly report on locations 1925–1926.
- AD 1765, Yearly report on locations 1926–1927.
- AD 1765, Annual report of Native Administration Department 1929–1930.
- AD 1765, Annual report of Native Administration Department 1931–1932.
- AD 1765, Report on locations 1936.
- II Newspapers
- Die Volksblad*, 19.10.1922.
- The Friend*, 6.1.1919, 13.5.1920, 25.8.1920, 5.5.1921, 27.6.1922, 16.11.1928, 3.9.1929, 6.11.1937.
- Umteteli wa Bantu*, 5.11.1921.
- III Articles in Newspapers
- HANDS, C.E. "Bobs" as beneficent victor: His fascinating entry into Bloemfontein, *The Bloemfontein Post*, 10.5.1900, p. 3.
- "OLD BLOEMFONTEINER" (pseudonym). When Bloemfontein's population is 250,000: Town-planning for the future, *The Friend*, 5.10.1936, p. 8.
- SOLOMON, E.J. Bloemfontein Native Location, *Umteteli wa Bantu*, 19.8.1922, p. 3.
- "THE VAGABOND" (pseudonym). Union's garden city: Beauty spots in the Free State capital, *The Friend*, 16.4.1927, p. 11.
- IV Books
- CAILLIÉ, R. *Travels through Central Africa to Timbuctoo and across the great desert, to Morocco performed in the years 1824–1828* (vol. 1). London, 1968.
- CRONJÉ, G. (Ed.). *Kultuurbeïnvloeding tussen blankes en bantoe in Suid-Afrika*. Pretoria, 1968.
- CURRIE, C. *Garden archaeology: A handbook*. York, 2005.
- DU PLESSIS, J. *A history of Christian missions in South Africa*. Cape Town, 1965.

- ELIOVSON, S. *Garden beauty of South Africa*. Johannesburg, 1979.
- HAVILAND, W.A. *Cultural anthropology*. Fort Worth, 1996.
- HOWARD, E. *Garden cities of to-morrow*. Eastbourne, 1985.
- HUXLEY, A. *An illustrated history of gardening*. New York, 1978.
- JELLICOE, G. et al. (Eds). *The Oxford companion to gardens*. Oxford, 1986.
- MANCOE, J. *First edition of the Bloemfontein Bantu and Coloured people's directory*. Bloemfontein, 1934.
- MORRIS, P. *A history of black housing in South Africa*. Johannesburg, 1981.
- SCHOEMAN, K. *Bloemfontein: Die ontstaan van 'n stad, 1846–1946*. Cape Town, 1980.
- VAN ZUYLEN, G. *The garden: Visions of paradise*. London, 1995.
- V Chapters in Books
- CONAN, M. From vernacular gardens to a social anthropology of gardening. In: M. Conan (Ed.), *Perspectives on garden histories* (Washington, D.C., 1999), pp. 181–204.
- GLEASON, K.L. To bound and to cultivate: An introduction to the archaeology of gardens and fields. In: N.F. Miller & K.L. Gleason (Eds), *The archaeology of garden and field* (Philadelphia, 1994), pp. 1–24.
- HUNT, J.D. Afterword. In: E. de Jong, *Nature and art: Dutch garden and landscape architecture, 1650–1740* (Philadelphia, 2000), pp. 157–158.
- MURRAY, S.-A. Indigenous gardening, belonging, and bewilderment: On becoming South African. In: Michael Chapman (Ed.), *Postcolonialism: South/African perspectives* (Newcastle, 2008), pp. 40–60.
- WESTMACOTT, R. The gardens of African-Americans in the rural South. In: J.D. Hunt & J. Wolschke-Bulmahn (Eds), *The vernacular garden* (Washington, D.C., 1993), pp. 77–105.
- ZANTKUYL, H. Stedelijke erven en tuinen tot omstreeks 1850. In: H. Zantkuyl et al., *Erf en tuin in oud-Amsterdam: De ontwikkeling van het besloten erf en de stadstuin in de oude binnenstad* (Amsterdam, 1982), pp. 9–59.
- VI Articles
- ANON. What is a Garden City? The example of Letchworth, *The South African Lady's Pictorial and Home Journal* XI(132), August 1921, p. 29.
- CLAPSON, M. The suburban aspiration in England since 1919, *Contemporary British History* 14(1), 2000, pp. 151–174.
- COETZER, N. Langa Township in the 1920s – an (extra)ordinary Garden Suburb, *South African Journal of Art History* 24(1), 2009, pp. 1–19.
- DU BRUYN, D. A garden is not a garden without a hedge: The story of the Segoe family's Batho garden, *Culna* 70, November 2015, pp. 11–13.
- DU BRUYN, D. Batho celebrates a century (1918–2018): The founding of Bloemfontein's “model location”, *Culna* 73, March 2019, pp. 2–4.
- DU BRUYN, D. Oral testimonies as a source of community history, with special reference to the Batho Project, Bloemfontein, *South African Journal of Cultural History* 24(2), November 2010, pp. 1–24.
- DU BRUYN, D. The story of a township garden: Mogrey's family recollections, *Culna* 68, November 2013, pp. 34–36.
- DU BRUYN, D. Township topiary – the African way, *Topiarius* 23, Summer 2019, pp. 37–40.
- DU BRUYN, D. ‘Township Topiary’: The history of the English-style gardens of Batho, Mangaung (1846–1948), *Navorsing van die Nasionale Museum, Bloemfontein* 27(3), December 2011, pp. 37–82.
- DU BRUYN, D. & M. OELOFSE, “The idea of beautifying the surroundings”: Bloemfontein's (Mangaung) Batho location a “garden location”? (c. 1918–1939), *New Contree* 84, July 2020, pp. 30–56.
- GINSBURG, R. “Now I stay in a house”: Renovating the matchbox in apartheid-era Soweto, *African Studies* 55(2), 1996, pp. 127–139.
- HEATH, B.J. & A. BENNETT, “The little spots allow'd them”: The archaeological study of African-American yards, *Historical Archaeology* 34(2), 2000, pp. 38–55.
- JACQUES, D. The progress of garden archaeology, *The Journal of Garden History* 17(1), 1997, pp. 3–10.
- MARITZ, C.J. Enkele politieke gevolge en implikasies van die akkulturasieproses vir Suid-Afrika, *Africanus* 6(1 & 2), November 1976, pp. 20–40.

- MAYLAM, P. Explaining the apartheid city: 20 years of South African urban historiography, *Journal of Southern African Studies* 21(1), March 1995, pp. 19–38.
- MURRAY, S.-A. The idea of gardening: Plants, bewilderment, and indigenous identity in South Africa, *English in Africa* 33(2), October 2006, pp. 45–65.
- PHILLIPS, H. The local state and public health reform in South Africa: Bloemfontein and the consequences of the Spanish 'Flu epidemic of 1918, *Journal of Southern African Studies* 13(2), January 1987, pp. 210–233.
- RHEINALLT JONES, J.D. & A.L. SAFFERY, Social and economic conditions of native life in the Union of South Africa, *Bantu Studies* VII(4), December 1933, pp. 317–340.
- SOMERVILLE, T.S. Our first garden city, *The Outspan* 2(38), 18.11.1927, p. 43.
- SWANSON, M.W. The sanitation syndrome: Bubonic plague and urban native policy in the Cape Colony, 1900–1909, *Journal of African History* XVIII(3), 1977, pp. 387–410.
- TORR, L. Providing for the “better-class native”: The creation of Lamontville, 1923–1933, *South African Geographical Journal* 69(1), 1987, pp. 31–46.
- TWALA, C. “Ulundi-Kaya”: The dwelling of Thomas Mtobi Mapikela in Bloemfontein (Mangaung) – its historical significance, *South African Journal of Cultural History* 18(1), June 2004, pp. 63–79.
- VAN DER BANK, D.A. Eduardiaanse invloede in die Oranje-rivierkolonie, *South African Journal of Cultural History* 10(1), May 1996, pp. 60–73.
- VAN DER WAAL, G.M. Aantekeninge oor party voorstede van Johannesburg, *Africana Notes and News* 21(2), June 1974, pp. 62–65.
- VAN ERP-HOUTEPEN, A. The etymological origin of the garden, *Journal of Garden History* 6(3), 1986, pp. 227–231.
- WILHELM, G. Dooryard gardens and gardening in the black community of Brushy, Texas, *Geographical Review* 65(1), January 1975, pp. 73–92.
- VII Dissertations
- BOTHA, S. *Die verandering en ontwikkeling van die woonhuisargitektuur in Bloemfontein gedurende die tydperk 1846–1946 met bydraende faktore*. Unpublished M.A. dissertation, University of the Orange Free State, 1991.
- CALDERWOOD, D.M. *Native housing in South Africa*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, University of the Witwatersrand, 1953.
- DU BRUYN, H.J. *Gardens, gardening culture and the development of a semi-vernacular garden style in Batho, Mangaung, 1918–1939: A historical perspective*. Unpublished Ph.D. thesis, University of the Free State, 2018.

Springboks, Spitfire bows and family archery – the National Museum Bloemfontein’s Du Plessis Collection and its national and international intersections

Hendrik Snyders*

*Centre for Military Studies, South African Military Academy, Saldanha 7395, South Africa
Department of History, University of the Free State, P.O. Box 339, Bloemfontein 9300, South Africa
E-mail: snydersh@sun.ac.za
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8630-4122>*

ABSTRACT

Despite being an integral part of the country’s sporting identity, the history of competitive archery remains a neglected area of South Africa’s sports history. Following its establishment in the 1860s as an elitist recreational activity characterised by social gatherings and merrymaking, it gradually developed into a well-organised and nationally coordinated sport during the 20th century. En route, it intersected with issues such as race, gender, professionalism, and politics, all of which collectively shaped its South African character. Due to a lack of original archives, none of the affiliated members of Archery South Africa have thus far documented their own illustrious past. This article, using the literature on artefact biographies, reconstructs the history of both South African and Free State archery with the aid of a small number of artefacts in the collection of the National Museum, Bloemfontein.

KEYWORDS: Apartheid, archery, Bloemfontein, Du Plessis, museum, Orange Free State, South Africa, sport

**This research was conducted and completed while the author was in the service of the National Museum, Bloemfontein*

INTRODUCTION

Included in the History Collection of the National Museum, Bloemfontein, are three trophies, all awarded for achievements in archery, and a beautifully made Grove’s ‘Spitfire’ bow (Fig. 1).¹ In addition, the collection includes a scrapbook, various newspaper cuttings, events programmes and tickets, photographs, private correspondence, three trophies, and other ephemera. The bow, the Groves Spitfire 42TH, is a recurve bow that was manufactured by American bowmaker, Harold Groves at the end of the 1950s and imported into South Africa. Groves’ products were traditionally manufactured from risers of rosewood, zebrawood, ebony, and various colours of fiberglass. Due to the Groves bow’s flexibility and ease of handling, over time it became known for its speed and quality, and for a significant period it was the preferred bow for international competition.² The trophies that currently form part of the Du Plessis Collection, in turn, included the Bloemfontein Sherwood Bowmen Men’s Championship Trophy³,

Orange Free State Women’s Provincial Championship Rembrandt Trophy⁴, and the Orange Free State Archery Association Men’s Gold Cup Trophy – all associated with local and regional history.⁵ These items were all donated to the museum by the Du Plessis family, resident in the city in 2009 and who were recipients of the trophies at one time or another.

Henry du Plessis represented the Free State in inter-provincial archery and in addition to winning the provincial title, he also became the national or South African champion in 1965. This was followed by his winning national colours and being selected to represent South Africa in the World Championship Tournament in Sweden later that year. He was, coincidentally, also appointed as the Springbok captain for this tour. Under normal circumstances, this would have made him a strong contender for a place in the South African Olympic Games team for both the scheduled 1964 and 1968 Olympic Games. South Africa was, however, excluded from both because of its racial policies.

- 1 National Museum, Bloemfontein Collection (hereafter NMB) 19486, Ex 2/12 – J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein
- 2 Anon., *Harold Groves – Groves Spitfire Bows*, <http://www.vintagearchery.org/groves-archery.html> (accessed: 23.10.2023).
- 3 NMB 19485, Ex 2/12 - J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein.
- 4 NMB 19484, Ex 2/12 - J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein.
- 5 NMB 19483, Ex 2/14 - J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein.

Figure 1: Du Plessis suitcase 1: Groves Spitfire 42TH bow, competition photographs and trophies. (photo: Marelle van Rensburg)

Henry's wife, Anna, was an equally skilled archer and she won the Free State women's archery championship more than once. She also represented the Free State in 1963 together with her husband. Their son, Willie, followed in their footsteps and became South Africa's junior archery champion in 1968 and again in 1970. In addition to artefacts, the donation also includes several newspaper clippings and photographs (Fig. 2) and it tells the story of one family's close ties with archery as a national sport during the 1960s. Furthermore, it gives an idea of local activity's intersections with both national and international events and, therefore, served as a lens into South African archery's turbulent history.

The history of archery, in general, is a largely unmaped landscape that is neither mentioned in G.A.

Parker's *South African Sports* published in 1897 or H.P. Swaffer's similarly named study published in 1914.⁶ Furthermore, historians such as K.C. Donaldson claim that the sport in South Africa was at best an ad hoc activity before 1930, and that target archery was only formally introduced during the 1930s. It is further claimed that archery as a codified and formal sporting activity was only formally introduced in Cape Town, Durban and Johannesburg by 1946.⁷ These claims, however, do not align with the available historical records. Contemporary newspapers, for example, indicated that the sport was widely practised in the Cape Colony (and Natal to a lesser extent) during the 19th century. In addition, archery equipment was available for sale in all the South African colonies, including the Orange Free

6 See G.A. Parker, *South African Sports* (London: Low, Marston & Co., 1897), *passim*; H.P. Swaffer (ed.), *South African Sport* (Johannesburg: Transvaal Leader, 1914), *passim*.

7 K.C. (ed.) Donaldson, *The South African Sporting Encyclopaedia and Who's Who* (Johannesburg: Donaldson Publications, 1949), p. 9.

Figure 2: Du Plessis suitcase 2: Scrapbook and ticket. (photo: Marelle van Rensburg)

State, from as far back as the 1850s. Given this situation and the fact that archery forms an integral part of South Africa's national sports identity, its past needs to be retrieved and inserted into the historical mainstream.⁸

Against this background, this study uses a combination of official and newspaper archives as well as secondary literature to reconstruct the history of archery in both Bloemfontein and South Africa to use it as a lens to investigate the intersection of local and international sports events with, and the impact it had

on individual and collective lives. The Johannesburg-based *Rand Daily Mail* was extensively used since it, more than the Cape Town or Natal papers, covered both regional and provincial event results in great detail. The main Orange Free State papers lacked detail.

FROM INDIVIDUAL TO CLUB ACTIVITY DURING THE 19TH CENTURY

A survey of historical newspapers indicated that some of the earliest advertisements for the sale of

8 F. van der Merwe & F. Cleophas, Mapping out an obscured South African sport history landscape through Edward Henderson history, *African Journal for Physical Health Education, Recreation and Dance* 17(2), 2011, p. 233.

archery equipment appeared in the local media in Cape Town as far back as the 1850s. During August 1853, T.J. Hitchcock of Shortmarket Street in Cape Town notified the public of the impending arrival of a shipment of goods including archery, crossbows and arrows.⁹ This and other advertisements were subsequently repeated throughout the decade. This seems to suggest that the intended clients were individual enthusiasts that imported their sport into the Cape Colony. The first recorded club, the Cape Town Archery Club, was founded in the city in 1862. A key driver in this regard was Katherine Mary Templer, the wife of the Governor of the Cape Colony, Sir Philip Wodehouse. Several others, including the Sea Point (Cape Town, 1863) and the Grahamstown clubs (1864) were subsequently founded. With no local manufacturer, equipment was imported from England, which, in turn, made it possible to initiate a formal competition.¹⁰ Shortly thereafter several clubs, involving both sexes, were established throughout the Cape Colony in both the main urban centres, such as Grahamstown (1865), and key rural towns, such as Cradock and Graaff-Reinet, during the 1860s. The eastern districts clubs formally launched their competition in February 1872 at an occasion attended by the Cape Governor, Lord Barkly.¹¹ Over the next two decades growth continued to be strong in the Cape Peninsula with more clubs being added such as Wynberg (1890), Westbrooke (c. 1894), San Souci, and Suburban (1899).¹² Similarly, in the eastern districts of the Cape Colony, and thanks to the efforts of the Ancient Order of Foresters, a new club in Port Elizabeth joined the archery fraternity.¹³

Outside the Cape Colony the sport also found favour with enthusiasts in neighbouring Natal with reports of an active club existing in Pietermaritzburg (est. 1878). Testifying to the ever-growing popularity of the sport, reports started to appear of the possibility of the establishment of an archery club for black women in Natal.¹⁴ Unfortunately, no detail about the individuals or collective behind the initiative was

reported. Two years before the end of the 19th century, enthusiasts established the Durban Archery Club on 12 August.¹⁵ Although no club activity was reported in the Transvaal and Orange Free State republics, some evidence such as newspaper advertisements indicated the existence of archery enthusiasts that motivated local dealers to start importing equipment for sale. One such advertisement which appeared in *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette* newspaper during 1881, offered archery equipment for sale in the Free State capital.¹⁶

The existing clubs were in most cases open to white members of colonial society of both sexes. Clubs such as the Cape Town-based Suburban Archery Club further drew its members exclusively from the ranks of the colonial bureaucrats employed by the colonial administration in Government House. It was, therefore, not surprising, judging by the regular media reports, that archery events were important and even lavish affairs that attracted a significant attendance. Some clubs, such as the Westbrooke Archery Club in Cape Town under the presidency of Reverend Canon George Ogilvie, a prominent individual in education, church and sporting circles, were active in running their own competitions, operated on a system of invited friends – suggesting a sense of exclusivity in operations.¹⁷ It was particularly the case in more distant areas such as in the rural parts of the eastern districts of the Cape Colony. Indeed, the *Eastern Province Herald* reported in December 1864 that the Cradock Ladies Archery Club had both a meeting and a very competitive contest, which they combined with an enjoyable tea.¹⁸ To emphasise its exclusivity and class character the Grahamstown club, for example, consistently held its club meetings, whether for the changing of club rules or ordinary business, on a Thursday afternoon at 15h00 – a time when most ordinary working-class enthusiasts were at work and unable to attend. Similarly, the *Transvaal Argus* reported that “private parties, concerts and theatricals, archery and croquet are, and have been

9 Anon., Hourly expected per 'Paramatta', *Mercantile Advertiser*, 6.8.1853, p. 8.

10 V. de Kock, *The fun they had: The pastimes of our forefathers* (Cape Town: Howard B. Timmins, 1955), pp. 158-159.

11 Anon., Marriage in high life, *Natal Witness*, 13.2.1872, p. 3.

12 See for example Anon., Archery club, *Cape Times*, 8.9.1890, p. 1; Anon., Archery, *Cape Times*, 25.4.1899, p. 7; Anon., San Souci Archery Society, *Cape Mercantile Advertiser*, 4.12.1867, p. 1; Anon., Archery club, *Cape Times*, 8.9.1890, p. 1.

13 Anon., Forrester's anniversary, *Eastern Province Herald*, 7.8.1895, p. 4.

14 Anon., Weekly Notes, *Port Elizabeth Telegraph*, 27.11.1883, p. 3.

15 Anon., An archery club, *Cape Times*, 13.8.1895, p. 5.

16 Anon., Important notice, *The Friend of the Free State and Bloemfontein Gazette*, 15.12.1881, p. 5.

17 Anon., Westbrooke Archery Club, *Cape Times*, 26.5.1894, p. 1.

18 Anon., Cradock, *Eastern Province Herald*, 13.12.1864, p. 3.

during the winter, all the rage”¹⁹ in the Graaff-Reinet district. Thus, when some females attended a ball of the local Graaff-Reinet Archery Club in simple ball dress, they were severely criticised for their poor taste of both dress and knowledge.²⁰ The *Cape Times* described one such archery gathering hosted in the Assembly Hall in Cape Town as a “numerous and fashionable assembly”.²¹

These trends and the prominence of the colonial higher middle-class and the local elite in archery affairs were not surprising and were consistent with practices overseas, where meetings of archery societies in both England and Wales were often characterised by the wearing of “outlandish costumes” and the hosting of “extravagant dinners”, and as opportunities for its female members and participants to show off their “feminine form” from the late 18th century well into the 19th century.²² An added attraction, arguably, was the close association of archery clubs in the colony with the British Royal Toxophilite Society, the control-body of the sport in the Mother Country, that had the British monarch as its patron.²³

The Anglo-Boer (South African) War (1899–1902) disrupted the first phase of local archery growth. Although some sporadic activity continued, no formal inter-colonial or inter-regional competitions were held because of martial law, lack of transport and the need for travel permits. This resulted in locals forfeiting an opportunity to participate in the first major event, namely the Paris Olympic Games. Archers in Cape Town, however, staged a fundraiser for the “Tommy’s Welcome to the Cape” campaign and contributed £2.1 to the fund as a demonstration of their loyalty to the British cause.²⁴

TOWARDS A NATIONAL SPORT, 1902–1949

During the war, the archery equipment remained an integral part of the products renowned sports goods

company, The Sports’ Depot, owned by Thurston & Co. of Greenmarket Square in Cape Town, offered for sale.²⁵ Their catalogue of goods was advertised in Cape, Rhodesian, and Mozambican newspapers throughout the period of conflict. This suggests that they had an established client-base interested in procuring the available products on offer. By the second half of 1901 and with the war starting to shift towards its final phase, some clubs such as Suburban in Cape Town that had succeeded in maintaining some activity, felt confident enough to start advertising for new members and to resume its normal activities.²⁶ By April and with the conflict nearing its end, competition was resumed at the Newlands Cricket Ground with 50 participants in attendance. Following the competition and awards ceremony, the gathering spent a “pleasant” day together.²⁷ By October 1902, with peace concluded, the club was actively busy hosting its domestic competition. Since it made use of the available cricket oval to host its events at an annual rent, it often had to reschedule their events so as not to interfere with the playing of cricket matches.

The period before the founding of the Union of South Africa (1910) was one of slow growth for the sport of archery. The most publicised and visible activity was largely Cape Town-based with little similar developments elsewhere. The available media reports indeed sketched a picture of fragmentation of a series of unlinked activity. Examples of these included a *Rand Daily Mail* feature on summer fashion, with a dress suitable for the “fair archer” that would not impede her prowess.²⁸ During the same period, St. Andrews, a new high school for girls in Parktown, Johannesburg, included facilities for archery in their layout and final building. The Transvaal media, like that of its Cape counterparts, however, continued to carry regular advertisements for archery equipment, which pointed to an ongoing interest in and of individual practice of the activity. The sport, in most cases, was often part of athletics events or social gatherings. In another positive

19 Anon., Monthly Notes from Graaff-Reinet”, *Transvaal Argus*, 4.9.1866, p. 3.

20 Anon., Graaff-Reinet Calico Ball, *Grahamstown Journal*, 9.10.1876, p. 2.

21 Anon., Local and General, *Eastern Province Herald*, 15.10.1867, p. 6.

22 M. Johnes, Archery, romance and elite culture in England and Wales, c. 1780–1840, *History* 89(294), 2004, pp. 193-208.

23 M. Huggins, Sport and the British upper classes c. 1500–2000: A historiographic overview, *Sport in History* 28(3), 2008, pp. 364-388.

24 Anon., Tommy’s welcome to the Cape, *Cape Times*, 2.2.1900, p. 5.

25 Anon., Thurston & Co., *Rand Daily Mail*, 13.1.1900, p. 4.

26 Anon., Suburban Archery Club, *Cape Times*, 19.9.1901, p. 4.

27 Anon., News of the Day, *Cape Times*, 14.4.1902, p. 5.

28 Anon., The latest holiday fashions, *Rand Daily Mail*, 6.8.1904, p. 13.

development the existence of an archery club in Pretoria was reported in the *Cape Daily Telegraph* in 1905.²⁹

The period after Unification was also characterised by slow growth of organised interclub and interprovincial archery. Individual practice thereof, however, continued as evidenced by the constant advertising of bows and arrows as individual items or as toys in the mainstream media. It also made an appearance in both insolvent and deceased estates and its associated auctions. In addition, local newspapers continued to publish reports about various overseas archery events, including the World Archery Championships and the Olympic Games. This helped to keep the sport in the public mind in the absence of organised competitions involving clubs and associations. In June 1914, the sport was also readmitted into the Olympic Games. Impeding factors were the start and duration of the First World War (1914–1918), the challenges of post-war reconstruction and the Great Flu (1918), and by 1929, the start of the Great Depression. Under these conditions, South Africa remained an interested observer of the international unfolding of the sport at events such as the Olympic Games.

The decade before the start of the Second World War (1939–1945) was equally characterised by slow growth. Archery, however, made a regular appearance as part of a comprehensive programme of entertainment. At the beginning of the 1930s, it was common to see it listed as part of the programme of venues and institutions such as the Moulin Rouge Co. “entertainment providers” in Johannesburg. Similarly, a golf course development in the Orange Free State town of Virginia, as part of its marketing campaign, advertised archery as a future offering beyond its normal programme.³⁰ The *Rand Daily Mail* further gave ample space to the coverage of the 1933 World Archery Championship at Ranelagh Club in the UK, where eight nations participated for the three-year-old title with the USA, France and Belgium as the favourites.³¹

Beyond the activities within the white community, the sport also received a timeous boost from the local Indian populace and the occasional tours of visiting Indian performers such as a group from the Baroda State, who had included archery as an integral part of their performance. During 1910, the Indian Athletic Association Troupe in Durban presented what was billed as “a sensational feats of archery and athletics” at the Electric Theatre.³² Archery was further combined with a display of dagger and knife throwing to entertain paying clients. During 1934, the visiting Indian Girl Guides staged various displays, including archery, before mixed audiences during their three month tour of the Union.³³ They performed, inter alia, at events at the Baragwanath Aerodrome in Johannesburg,³⁴ the Masonic Hall in Krugersdorp and at the Johannesburg City Hall.³⁵ In addition, the feats of the travelling Indian entertainer, under the stage name “Professor Yashpal”, hosted by the Transvaal United Patidar Society, Transvaal Hindu Educational Council and Young Men Hindu Association collectively, received wide publicity. During his a month-long tour of the Union of South Africa in 1937, he performed in front of mixed audiences of whites and people of colour at venues such as the Inchcape Hall in Johannesburg and Durban.³⁶ His performance included various feats involving a variety of archery tricks, which were presented as part of the “ancient arts of India” and in which he demonstrated “astonishing mastery”.³⁷ This was augmented by reports the following year of the involvement of three South Africans on the movie set of the film *Robin Hood*, in which Errol Flynn played the leading role.³⁸

In the first year of the Second World War, and concomitant with the 1939 World Archery Championships held in Paris, France, the first recorded club in Transvaal was established. Named the Adventurer’s Archery Club, it was founded in Johannesburg by Captain Wally Vane-Wallace. The club had a mixed

29 Anon., Pretoria News, *Cape Daily Telegraph*, 28.3.1905, p. 5.

30 Anon., Moulin Rouge, *Rand Daily Mail*, 12.12.1931, p. 9. See also Anon., Northcliff Weekend Recreation Club, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.10.1939, p. 8.

31 Anon., Revival of archery, *Rand Daily Mail*, 2.8.1933, p. 11.

32 Anon., Electric Theatre, *Indian Opinion*, 1.1.1910, p. 23.

33 Anon., Indian girls are expert with ..., *Rand Daily Mail*, 15.8.1934, p. 11.

34 Anon., Flip for Indian Girl Guides, *Rand Daily Mail*, 28.8.1934, p. 14.

35 Anon., Indian Girl Guides Display, *Rand Daily Mail*, 27.8.1934, p. 7.

36 Anon., At the Inchcape Hall, *Bantu World*, 4.9.1937, p. 5.

37 Anon., Professor Yashpal, *Rand Daily Mail*, 25.8.1937, p. 11; Anon., Indian stops his pulse and lives: Yogi’s great feats, *Rand Daily Mail*, 25.8.1937, p. 13.

38 Anon., Three South Africans in ‘Robin Hood’, *Rand Daily Mail*, 10.1.1938, p. 7.

membership (men and women) and committed itself to work towards the establishment of a Transvaal Association. To overcome problems with acquiring bows and arrows, it resorted to manufacturing its own equipment. In the absence of proper facilities, it used the open spaces in Irene and Kenilworth for practices and competitions.³⁹ The Adventurers were soon after joined by the Robin Hoods Archery Club which it immediately engaged in competition.⁴⁰ This effectively established an organised archery presence in three of the four provinces of the Union of South Africa. As the war got underway, the Orange Free State was the only area without a known club presence.

During the war, domestic archery activity remained low, and its growth was in fact severely constrained. Right at the start of the war in September 1939, the Inanda Club in Durban hosted a “war gymkhana”, inclusive of archery as part of the “sideshow” to raise funds for the Mayor’s Food Fund.⁴¹ Thereafter the sport, like its other counterparts, effectively disappeared from the news for the rest of the conflict. Already struggling to make the transition towards a fully-fledged local activity, this decline made its revival so much more difficult. Following the conclusion of the war, archery enthusiasts in Cape Town, Durban and Johannesburg started to revive the sport. Notable personalities in this regard were individuals such as former Pole and world champion Irena Shorupska, Alfred Sewell and Sam Hikins, respectively.⁴² One of the first new clubs to be founded in the Transvaal in the immediate post-war period was the Brakpan Archery Club in 1947. They received general assistance from the long-established Morena Club when the former hosted their “sports tableau”.⁴³ On a regular basis Morena presented what was called “daring archery exhibitions” in the city – a development that contributed to the further revival of the sport. Other initiatives included the hosting of innovative events such as an “archery tea gardens” to awaken public interest.⁴⁴

A year later, with the number of Witwatersrand clubs having increased to six, the Pretoria club hosted the first

Transvaal Archery Championship Tournament in June 1948 at Loftus Versfeld in the city.⁴⁵ The participating clubs, which also became the founding members of the Transvaal Archery Association on the occasion, were Morena, Brakpan, Louis Trichardt, Poison Arrow, Pretoria, and Krugersdorp, plus a number of individual players from Nelspruit (Mbombela). At this point, the number of archery clubs nationally stood at 25 individual and active bodies spread over the different provinces and steadily became more representative of a growing working-class and semi-rural membership base. This laid the foundation for the founding of a national body, the South African Toxophilite Society, established under the leadership of Matt Sluyter, consisting of Transvaal, Western Province and Natal, later that year. The only remaining entity was the Orange Free State, the fourth province of the Union of South Africa. Without avail, the new body affiliated to the Federation International de Tir a l’Arch (FITA), which would allow the country participation in key events such as the world championships, Empire Games and Olympic Games.⁴⁶

ARCHERY FROM APARTHEID TO SHARPEVILLE, 1950–1960

Following its electoral victory in 1948, the Reunited National Party of South Africa (Herengigde Nasionale Party; HNP), who campaigned the general election on a political platform that promised white voters institutionalized segregation, started to promulgate various laws to achieve its objectives. Amongst the legislated measures were the *Prohibition of Mixed Marriages Act* (Act no. 55 of 1949), the *Population Registration Act* (Act no. 30 of 1950), the *Group Areas Act* (Act no. 41 of 1951), the *Separate Representation of Voters Act* (Act no. 46 of 1951), the *Reservation of Separate Amenities Act* (Act no. 49 of 1953), and the *Native Laws Amendment Act* (Act no. 54 of 1952). The stipulations of the *Population Registration Act*, which had for the purposes of governance, subdivided the South African population along racial lines, was, according to Keith Breckenridge, “the bureaucratic

39 R.M. Graham, Archery came to the Transvaal, *Rand Daily Mail*, 17.5.1939, p. 3.

40 Anon., Archery at Irene, *Rand Daily Mail*, 15.5.1939, p. 16.

41 Anon., Vanity Fair, *Rand Daily Mail*, 28.9.1939, p. 9.

42 S. Hikins, Archery, in K.C. Donaldson (ed.), *The South African Sporting Encyclopaedia and Who’s Who* (Johannesburg: Donaldson Publications, 1949), p. 9.

43 Anon., Brakpan sports tableau, *Rand Daily Mail*, 30.1.1948, p. 13.

44 Anon., Miscellaneous – Archery Tea Gardens, *Rand Daily Mail*, 4.10.1946, p. 2.

45 Anon., True as an arrow’s flight, *Rand Daily Mail*, 28.6.1948, p. 7.

46 M. Eorwine, Archery – ‘Field takes off’, in B. Deans (ed.), *Allied Book of South African Sport and Sports Records, 1988–89* (Randburg: SASBOR, 1989), p. 18.

cornerstone of the apartheid state, the lynch-pin of the Group Areas Act".⁴⁷ Collectively, this suite of legislation outlawed inter-racial marriages and sexual relations, provided for separate residential areas, prohibited racial social mixing in most areas of life, and removed blacks from the common voters roll.

The apartheid authorities further used the *Suppression of Communism Act* (Act no. 44 of 1950) to repress any resistance against their policies. Although there was no specific legislation passed to formalise segregated sport, black athletes continued to be excluded from national teams. The *Reservation of Separate Amenities Act* (Act no. 49 of 1953) left black communities with minimal facilities. Archery, still in the process of developing a national profile, therefore, entered its new era, like all other sports, as a racially exclusive activity. By 1952, with the celebration of the Van Riebeeck Sports Festival, an event aimed at celebrating the tercentenary of the landing of the Dutch colonists under Jan van Riebeeck (1652), archery became further enmeshed in the politics of apartheid. On the occasion which was boycotted by the black community, Polish and Western Province champion and South African resident Irene Shorupska, competed in an archery contest with two "Bushmen" at the Festival Fair in Cape Town during April 1952.⁴⁸ Beyond the festival, the South African Airforce Association offered archery as part of their morning market fundraising activities while the South African National Championship, as decided in Colesberg previously, took place in Durban.⁴⁹

In 1953, the practice of archery in Bloemfontein, specifically the activities of the local Sherwood Bowmen Archery Club, formally came to the national attention. It boasted amongst the club membership, esteemed individuals such as Appeal Court Judge Van den Heever, a fact that attracted the attention of the Johannesburg-based newspaper, the *Rand Daily Mail*.⁵⁰ Furthermore, the club made news during August when its two members, Bill Grant and Bob Attree, set a new South African record of striking a target at 320 yards with the 60 pounds bow, thrice in one week. The new record was, however, not

recognised since it was set during a local rather than an interprovincial event, thus unofficial.⁵¹ This feat was significant enough for others in the archery fraternity to take note of. During its inaugural year, the Sherwood Bowmen Club further introduced its Championship Trophy for the Bloemfontein Archery Championship, which was donated by Kurt Schmidt, a local businessman. The first recipients of the floating trophy, which was competed for in November, were a married couple, Jan and Lal Jacobs, who won the male and female sections respectively. The runners up were Bill Grand and Eric Prince.⁵² Thereafter, this trophy was continuously awarded until 1965.

Following its entry into competitive archery, Bloemfontein hosted its first South African championships a year later. Attended by several clubs from across the country, competitions provided for several categories, including long and short distance, national flight shoot, inter-club and provincial title. Testifying to its undoubted depth amongst its archers, the local club finished in the second position in the Provincial Shoot, after Iscor. This set the stage for overall improvement at the next year's championship held at the Iscor Club in Pretoria. On this occasion, R. Botha of Bloemfontein won the Women's Short Distance. Furthermore, the Bloemfontein Club finished in second place in the interclub category, while the Free State finished second in the interprovincial category. To top it off, Eric Prince finished second in the Men's Short Distance category.⁵³

The 1955 season saw the number of registered archery clubs country-wide rapidly increasing to 750 registered individual archers. This development coincided with the sport being included in the Witwatersrand University's Town's Festival, which provided the activity with much-needed additional advertising. Continuing the same growth trajectory, the Bloemfontein archers yet again participated in the national championship held in Benoni in June. They returned from this event with members B. Els having won the Junior Championship and A. de Beer the National Flight Shoot. In addition, S. Botha (Bloemfontein) finished second in the men's division

47 K. Breckenridge, *The Book of Life: The South African population register and the invention of racial descent, 1950–1980*, *Kronos* 40(1), 2014, p. 225.

48 Anon., Archers three, *Rand Daily Mail*, 7.4.1952, p. 10.

49 Anon., Colesberg, *Rand Daily Mail*, 6.11.1951, p. 12.

50 Anon., Flying Judge sells plane, buys bicycle, *Rand Daily Mail*, 4.11.1953, p. 11.

51 Anon., Archery record is unofficial, *Rand Daily Mail*, 6.8.1953, p. 12.

52 Anon., Man and wife win archery contest, *Rand Daily Mail*, 3.11.1953, p. 6.

53 Anon., Archery S.A. Championship, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.4.1955, p. 4.

after Ronnie Hunter, the South African Champion. His team mate R. Botha (Bloemfontein), in turn, became the new women's national champion. They concluded the year with four local archers, D.S. Botha, Jan Jacobs, C. Breytenbach and Eric Prince scoring more than 800 points in a single competition for a South African record.⁵⁴ This season further saw Ronnie Hunter of Pretoria becoming the country's first national representative or "Springbok" at the World Championships in Finland where he finished in the 10th position.

Following their successful performances in the preceding national tournament, the Bloemfontein archery fraternity met the new season with increased confidence. They duly entered the field in April 1956 at Pietermaritzburg and returned from there with two finalists amongst the top male players. Members D.S. Botha and C. Breytenbach finished in second and fifth place, respectively.⁵⁵ This was followed by the Free State archers entering the Transvaal Championships at Vanderbijl Park. The local clubs, especially Iscor, however, proved to be too strong which resulted in the visitors returning to Bloemfontein without any honours.⁵⁶ This season also witnessed the Orange Free State Archery Association inaugurated the Men's Gold Cup Competition. The competition trophy was presented by Maitland Jewellers of Bloemfontein and C. Breytenbach became its first recipient. This floating trophy, based on the engraved information on the artefact's body, was likewise continuously awarded until 1972.

The 1957 season was another notable year in South African archery history. In continuing to expand the country's profile overseas, Bill White of the Zoo Lake Morena Archery Club in Johannesburg, represented South Africa at the World Archery Championship and World Archery Congress in Prague, Czechoslovakia, in July. He was, however, not awarded Springbok colours because of not having won the national title. The rationale behind his selection was merely coincidental with the archery authorities exploiting White's travelling to Europe in

his private capacity to stake a claim for itself as a sporting country of note. Furthermore, the position was that national colours would be awarded once he had achieved "Springbok standards", i.e. beating opponents during the world competition.⁵⁷ On the local front, the April South African Championship, which was held in Emmerentia, Johannesburg, saw B. Duncan (Bloemfontein Sherwood Club) achieving second place in the South African Junior Beginners Championship, while N. Duncan also made an impression in the same division.⁵⁸ In another boost for Free State archery, 18 July 1957 saw the establishment of the Virginia Archery Club with 20 members. This was preceded by an event of even greater significance, namely the first recorded incidence of training in archery of disabled people at the Avalon Centre for Disabled in Johannesburg.⁵⁹

In April 1958, the national championships returned to the Free State capital. Contrary to expectations, none of the local archers won any prizes.⁶⁰ In the men's section, Mervin Hurst (Iscor) dominated proceedings and walked away with the championship title. The disappointment and lack of honours for the hosts was, however, mitigated when three Bloemfontein archers, namely Jannie and Lal Jacobs as well as Mrs Van der Berg, were included in the 11-member national team to represent South Africa at the world championships in Belgium.⁶¹ The year 1959 saw the inauguration of the Orange Free State Provincial Women's Championship Trophy. This competition's floating trophy was donated by Rembrandt Furnishers in Bloemfontein. As was the case with the Sherwood Bowmen's Trophy, and based on the engravings on the artefact, the winner and first recipient were Lal Jacobs, one of the most experienced archers in the local circuit. On the national front, the prospects for the sport improved significantly with discussions about South Africa's possible entry into the Stoke-Mandeville Games in England for the disabled the following year, in addition to further participation in the world championships scheduled for Oslo, Norway, in 1961. The national interprovincial championship, in turn, took place in Durban.⁶²

54 Anon., Archery record, *Rand Daily Mail*, 17.11.1955, p. 16.

55 Anon., Hunter's 3rd title in a row, *Rand Daily Mail*, 2.4.1956, p. 13.

56 Anon., Archer sends arrow 433 yds: S.A. record, *Rand Daily Mail*, 5.6.1956, p. 9.

57 Anon., Archer for World Championships, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.6.1957, p. 10.

58 Anon., National Archery Results, *Rand Daily Mail*, 23.4.1957, p. 4.

59 Anon., Sister Iris takes a bow, *Rand Daily Mail*, 11.5.1957, p. 3.

60 Anon., Hurst retain archery title, *Rand Daily Mail*, 7.4.1958, p. 12.

61 Anon., Archers choose 11 for Brussels, *Rand Daily Mail*, 9.4.1958, p. 16.

62 Anon., Rest of sport in brief, *Rand Daily Mail*, 31.3.1959, p. 15.

FROM SHARPEVILLE TO INTERNATIONAL EXCLUSION, 1960–1970

On the 21 March 1960, South Africa exploded in an orgy of violence following the police killing of 69 demonstrators at Sharpeville on the Witwatersrand following an anti-pass march aimed at forcing the abolition of restrictions on the freedom of movement of blacks. In its wake, several so-called “backlash demonstrations” were organised by various political organisations.⁶³ As the unrest spread across the country, the apartheid regime banned several political organisations, including the African National Congress (ANC) and Pan Africanist Congress (PAC) under the *Unlawful Organisations Act* (Act no. 34 of 1960). Utilising the protection and cover of a declared state of emergency, the law enforcement agencies further used all the means at their disposal to repress opponents of the system and detained, killed, or exiled scores of activists.⁶⁴

Following the Sharpeville events, the *American Committee on Africa* (ACOA) started a *South Africa Emergency Campaign* and issued a “Call to Action” imploring ordinary Americans to join the worldwide boycott of South Africa. It further protested South Africa’s scheduled participation in the Olympic Games in Rome during the same period.⁶⁵ In addition, Dr Martin Luther King Jr. and Oliver Tambo (president of the exiled ANC), issued a joint “Appeal for Action Against Apartheid” (AAAA). This call was soon taken up by anti-apartheid activists and solidarity organisations on both sides of the Atlantic, who started to organise a diverse range of sector-specific movements. One of the first responders was the Campaign Against Race Discrimination in Sport (CARDIS) established by, among others, Father Trevor Huddleston, an Anglican priest and apartheid critic, one year before the Sharpeville shootings. From the onset, the CARDIS strived to end all whites-

only sports tours and it was one of the first to call for the total isolation of the apartheid state and was thus supportive of the call for a cultural boycott.⁶⁶

The first cultural boycott against apartheid South Africa in the “search for a much larger, multi-textured effort to achieve far-reaching alterations” was initiated by the *British Musicians Union* (BMU) during 1961, whose members refused to perform before segregated audiences. Additionally, they refused performance rights to South African theatres, which practiced racial segregation and discriminated on the basis of race. The effectiveness of this campaign was strengthened when members of the *British Screenwriters Guild*, *British Equity*, *American Equity*, as well as individual British, Irish and American playwrights joined the boycott during the decade.⁶⁷ This notwithstanding, South Africa participated in the World Championships in Oslo. The team, led by Bloemfontein archer, Jannie Jacobs, performed commendably and the South African women’s team finished in third position, after the USA and England.⁶⁸ On the home front, Welkom hosted the national championships.

As the campaign to exclude South Africa from international participation intensified during the next season, the national body started to prepare for participation in the Wheelchair Games and Empire Games, which were both scheduled to be hosted by Australia. The national championship, in turn, was set for Paarl during the Easter weekend. The Free State Archery Championships, on the other hand, were held in Virginia and won by two members of the local Harmony Archery Club in May 1962.⁶⁹ On the international front, the national team captured the gold medal at the Stoke-Mandeville Games in July 1962.⁷⁰

In 1963, Henry du Plessis was awarded Free State provincial colours for archery. He soon became the

63 R.A. Francisco, The dictator’s dilemma, in C. Davenport, H. Johnston & C. Mueller (eds), *Repression and mobilization* 64(2) (Minneapolis/London: University of Minnesota Press, 2005), p. 71.

64 K.A. O’Brien, Counter-intelligence for counter-revolutionary warfare: The South African police security branch 1979–1990, *Intelligence and National Security*, 16(3), 2001, p. 29.

65 American Committee on Africa (ACOA), *South Africa Emergency Campaign: A Call to Action, April 1960*. Available from African Activist Archives, Michigan State University (<https://www.africanactivist.msu.edu>), no p. no.

66 T. Huddleston, *Naught for your comfort* (Glasgow: Collins, 1956), p. 150.

67 E.S. Reddy, Cultural boycott: Statement by Director of U.N. Centre Against Apartheid: Press briefing. Available from <https://bdsmovement.net/news/cultural-boycott-statement-enuga-s-reddy-director-un-centre-against-apartheid-press-briefing> (accessed: 1.3.2019), no p. no.

68 Anon., S.A. placings in archery events, *Rand Daily Mail*, 15.8.1961, p. 18.

69 Anon., Virginia, *Rand Daily Mail*, 14.5.1962, p. 18.

70 Anon., Paralysed Springboks cheered! *Rand Daily Mail*, 30.7.1962, p. 2.

provincial archery champion and by 1965 he won the national championship. Henry was included in the national team to compete in the World Championship Tournament in Sweden in July 1965. He was, coincidentally, also the Springbok captain for this tour. Under normal circumstances, this would have made him a strong contender for a place in the South African Olympic Games team for both the scheduled 1964 and 1968 Olympic Games in Japan and Mexico. The country was, however, excluded from both because of its racial policies. This, nonetheless, did not dampen the enthusiasm, motivation and competitiveness of the Du Plessis family judged by their continued participation in competitive archery based on the trophy engravings.

Henry's wife, Anna, was an equally skilled archer in her own right and won the Free State women's archery championship more than once. She also represented Free State in 1963 together with her husband. Their son, Willie, followed in his parents' footsteps and became South Africa's junior archery champion in 1968 and again in 1970. This period, however, saw the demise of the Bloemfontein Sherwood Bowmen Championship Trophy Competition. In addition, in December 1968, the United Nations General Assembly adopted Resolution 2396 that called upon member states and associated organisations to suspend all cultural, educational, sports and other exchanges with the apartheid government, its organisations and institutions.⁷¹

Although some South African sports teams such as the national rugby team were still able to tour overseas during late 1969 and 1970, this was confronted by mass protests in the United Kingdom and Ireland. At the head of these protests were the anti-apartheid group *Stop All Racist Tours* (SART) led by Peter Hain, an exiled South African supported by several trade unions. Within this context, John Lennon of the *Beatles*, confidentially assisted with the payment of the fines of several arrested protestors.⁷² Whether the earlier banning of the music of the *Beatles* in South Africa played a role in this decision is, however, not clear. In 1970, several South African sports

bodies lost their international affiliation and were cut off from any further international participation. Given this collective pressure, South Africa was not only expelled from the International Olympic Committee but also from several other world sports bodies between 1964 and post-1970. These events are indelibly etched into the history of South Africa's sporting history.

Facing an uncertain future, some South African sports federations demanded action from the Department of Sport and Recreation, who, with due consideration to its central constituency, chose to reiterate the government's opposition to any form of racial mixing. It further rejected all external pressure for change and insisted that South Africa alone would decide who to invite and play against. This inflexibility generated increasingly violent opposition to all-white South African teams at international events, forcing them to consider some changes of a political nature. However, it came too late for the likes of the Du Plessis family. Although South Africa, thanks to its Western allies, maintained its membership and continued to enjoy a modicum of international competition, its national archery association had to do so as an unrepresented field archery association and not as a body representative of a nation.⁷³ Therefore, its athletes became the true victims of the reluctance of politicians to move beyond their vested interests, a situation that remained until 1991 and the start of South Africa's political transition.

ASSESSMENT

Based on the aforementioned events, South Africa in general, and Bloemfontein in particular, have a rich and multi-layered archery history that is not always appreciated. In this era of mass media and the dominance of sports like rugby, soccer and cricket, individual sports on the margins continued to be overlooked despite their contribution to the country's national sporting identity. The current research is aimed at contributing to foreground one such sport with a view to aiding the writing of a more comprehensive history. Furthermore, the

71 United Nations, *The United Nations and Apartheid, 1948–1994* (New York: Department of Public Information, United Nations, 1994), p. 356.

72 Anon., Government's 30-year-old files reveal ugly side of Springboks tour that brought shame on our nation: Day John Lennon paid my demo fine, *Herald* (Scotland), 1 January 2001. Available from <https://www.heraldsotland.com/news/12157956.governments-30-year-old-files-reveal-ugly-side-of-springboks-tour-that-brought-shame-on-our-nation-day-john-lennon-paid-my-demo-fine> (accessed: 5.4.2018), no p. no.

73 Anon., SA wins 3 medals at great world shoot, *Rand Daily Mail*, 24.8.1984, p. 5.

aforementioned events conclusively proved that artefacts are indeed storied “probe objects”⁷⁴ that contain “much about a nation’s sporting culture and the social, economic, and political milieu in which it developed”.⁷⁵ The life and collections of artefacts

associated with individual athletes, their clubs and associations, are therefore a useful lens for the investigation of a range of wider issues, including questions such as class, nationhood, ethnicity, race, sexuality and gender.⁷⁶

-
- 74 S. Benford, A. Hazzard, A. Chamberlain, K. Glover, C. Greenhalgh, L. Xu, M. Hoare & D. Darzentas, *Accountable Artefacts, Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - CHI '16* (New York: ACM Press, 2016), no p. no.
- 75 W. Vamplew, Facts and artefacts: Sports historians and sports museums, *Journal of Sport History* 25(2), 1998, p. 268.
- 76 D. Allen, 'National heroes': Sport and the creation of icons, *Sport in History* 33(4), 2013, p. 584.

INDAGO: INSTRUCTIONS TO AUTHORS

GENERAL

Indago: Investigating nature and humanity in Africa, is a DHET-accredited, open access journal that seeks to promote knowledge of African natural and cultural heritage by publishing high-quality, peer-reviewed scientific research. Previously known as *Navorsing van die Nasionale Museum*, *Indago* is published by the National Museum, Bloemfontein, South Africa. Manuscripts relevant to all topics of the natural and human sciences in Africa are accepted, including but not limited to anthropology, archaeology, history, fine arts, botany, palaeontology and zoology. Authors are entirely responsible for statements, whether fact or opinion. Manuscripts are considered on the understanding that they have not been submitted elsewhere for prior or simultaneous publication. Manuscripts are reviewed by at least two independent referees and approved by the Editorial Board before acceptance. Articles are first published online (www.nationalmuseumpublications.co.za) as soon as they are ready; hard copy issues are printed yearly and contain reprints of papers published in the preceding year.

INDAGO EDITORIAL POLICY

The journal is open to scholars not directly associated with the National Museum. Manuscripts containing original research results, as well as review papers and smaller contributions (short communications and case studies, up to four printed pages) consistent with the scope of the journal will be considered. All manuscripts should be written in clear, concise English (British or American standard). Authors whose mother tongue is not English are strongly urged to have their papers reviewed linguistically before submission; inadequately prepared manuscripts will be returned without consideration. There is no page limit to the length of manuscripts, but exceptionally long (over 100 pages) contributions, as well as proposals of special issues and refereed conference proceedings, should be discussed with the Editor-in-Chief. All contributions will be critically evaluated by at least two independent external referees; peer-review process is double-blind for manuscripts in humanities and single-blind for natural science contributions. Submissions may include online supplementary material.

The publisher of *Indago* recognises the need for transformative research that does not perpetuate stereotypes, discriminatory practices or undermine the rights and dignity of marginalised communities (whether defined on the basis of race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, gender, religion or disability). The publisher acknowledges the need to dismantle systemic racism and discrimination, and will not entertain material that expresses bias or prejudice or that misuses science to perpetuate colonial misconceptions and inequalities. The publisher also reserves the right to reject manuscripts that perpetuate biases or inequalities, and to subject any submissions relating to marginalised communities to a greater degree of academic scrutiny at the discretion of the Editorial Board.

For criteria of authorship, prospective contributors are urged to consult *Indago*'s Editorial Policy & Publication Ethics and Malpractice Statement.

The Editor-in-Chief's decision whether or not to accept a manuscript is final.

Contributions should be forwarded to the Editor-in-Chief of *Indago* by e-mail: indago@nasmus.co.za.

PREPARATION OF MANUSCRIPTS (all manuscripts)

Manuscripts should be submitted in Microsoft Word, 12 pt Times New Roman font, 1.5-spaced and in A4 format with 25 mm margins all around. Number manuscript pages consecutively beginning with the title page. Do not insert line numbers. Authors must **not** use Reference Managers and text styles other than unmodified Normal when preparing their manuscripts for submission.

Give full details of the **title** of the manuscript, **name(s)** of author(s), **postal address**, **e-mail address** and **ORCID** (if available) for each author, each on a separate line. The title of the paper should be informative but concise. A short running title (for page headlines) should be provided.

The **abstract**, summarising the contents of the paper and indicating the relevance of the work, should not usually exceed 30 type-written lines or 300 words. Adopt standard scientific nomenclature and avoid abbreviations and references. Select a set of up to 10 **keywords** (index terms). Authors are encouraged to provide a translation of the abstract and keywords in another appropriate language after acceptance of their manuscripts.

Numbers one to nine inclusive should be spelled out and numbers starting 10 onwards should be given in numerals. In a series, use numerals throughout. Dates in the text should be written as 4 August 1974, and times of the day as 08:00. Ranges are to be separated by an en-dash (–), not a hyphen (-).

Sources of funding for research or publication should always be disclosed in Acknowledgements, if applicable.

Illustrations and tables

When preparing illustrations and tables, consider the journal's full page size (170×250 mm) or one column size (82×250 mm). Illustrations (including graphs) and their captions or legends should form a separate, self-explanatory unit. Explain abbreviations in the captions, or (if too numerous) collect them elsewhere in a list (preferably under Materials and Methods). Multipart figures should be labelled as A, B *etc.* Use *sans serif* font (12–14 pt, bold face) for labels, preferably Arial or Helvetica. If the editor is to insert the final lettering, provide an overlay showing your requirements. Where necessary, illustrations (if not schematic) must include a scale bar. Do **not** frame illustrations. When preparing illustrations in Adobe Photoshop authors are advised to retain a copy of unflatten image with labelling on separate layers.

Tables should include headings and explanations, and should be numbered consecutively; tables must **not** be submitted as MS Excel files or graphic files (CDR, JPG, PNG, TIF *etc.*). Approximate positions of figures and tables should be indicated in the text. References in the text to illustrations and tables: Fig. 1; Figs 13–33; Table 1 (Note: Do not capitalise fig., figs, table, pl., pls, when referring to items reproduced in someone else's work). The format for figure captions is as follows:

Figure 5: Cottage-style planting in a Batho garden enclosed by a tall-clipped privet hedge, Makgothi Street, Batho, 2011. (National Museum, Bloemfontein: NM Photo Batho 211)

Figures 11–14: *Oryzaephilus* spp., median lobe of aedeagus and parameres (11–13) and male genitalia (14): (11) *O. abeillei* (Guillebeau); (12) *O. fauveli* (Reitter); (13) *O. mercator* (Fauvel); (14) *O. surinamensis* (Linnaeus). Scale bars = 50 μ m.

Authors are responsible for obtaining written permission from the publisher to reproduce any previously published tables or figures.

Ethical clearance

Indago accepts manuscripts on the condition that the reported research follows relevant national and international ethical guidelines and legislation, including (but not restricted to) personal data protection laws. The authors are responsible for obtaining a formal ethical clearance from relevant authorities where applicable, and should provide a proof thereof when they submit their manuscripts to *Indago*. The authors are responsible to ensure and, when possible, document that legal requirements pertaining to their work are fulfilled. *Indago* reserves the right to request documented proof of ethical clearance prior to considering a manuscript. Should a successfully reviewed and published manuscript garner criticism, the author(s) will have the opportunity for reply and rebuttal in a later issue of the journal.

Initial submission

An electronic version should be submitted to the Editor-in-Chief via email (indago@nasmus.co.za). Large files exceeding 10 MB are to be sent via WeTransfer. The text of the manuscript should be saved as a MSOffice Word document (DOC, DOCX) or Rich Text Format (RTF) file for text and tables, and JPEG (JPG), PNG, or LZW-compressed TIF file(s) for figures. Tables must **not** be submitted as MSOffice Excel files. Graphics must **not** be embedded in the text file, and may be of reduced quality sufficient for evaluation by reviewers. Manuscripts submitted in unsuitable formats will not be processed and the authors will be asked to re-submit them in an appropriate form.

Final submission

The final text accepted for print must be supplied in an editable electronic format. Easily intertransferable formats such as MSOffice Word document (DOC, DOCX) or Rich Text Format (RTF) are preferred. Mac users should submit the text in a format directly transferable to PC. Graphics are to be provided as LZW-compressed TIF or PNG files. Consult the editor in advance if you intend to submitting illustrations as vector graphics. **NEVER** import graphics into a word processor format (e.g., as DOC or RTF files). Refrain from mixing black-and-white (line) drawings and half-tone (grey)/colour illustrations in one file. Required modes and **minimum** resolutions for graphic files: colour in 8-bit per channel RGB mode, 300 dpi at print size (170/82×250 mm); half-tone in 8-bit greyscale mode, 300 dpi at print size; line art in black-and-white mode, at least 600 dpi at print size. However, it is advisable to submit figures prepared with a higher resolution.

CONTRIBUTIONS IN NATURAL SCIENCES

Where appropriate, the title should contain names of the higher taxa, typically the order and family, e.g. (Diptera: Phoridae). Abstracts of taxonomic papers should mention all nomenclatural acts and list all newly proposed nominal taxa. The suggested order of sections for original papers is: Introduction, Materials and Methods, Results/Taxonomy, Discussion and Conclusions (these may be combined), Acknowledgements, References, *Tables, *Figure legends. Begin the asterisked sections on new pages. Number footnotes consecutively throughout the text and use them sparingly.

Use up to three heading levels:

LEVEL 1 (e.g. **DISCUSSION**)

Level 2 (e.g. **Statistical analysis**)

Level 3 (e.g. *Mating and oviposition*)

Taxonomic papers must comply with all requirements of the current *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature* and *International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants*. Recommendations of the codes should also be followed. All newly described taxa and newly proposed *nomina*, new synonyms and new combinations should be explicitly designated as such, e.g. fam. n., trib. n., gen. n., sp. n., comb. n., nom. nov., syn. n.; *nomen conservandum* and *nomen rejiciendum* are abbreviated as nom. cons. and nom. rej., respectively; *nomen dubium*, *nomen nudum*, *nomen oblitum* and *nomen protectum* are not abbreviated.

For taxonomic papers, the suggested order of sections within a species/genus treatment is: Chresonymy, Type species (compulsory for new genera, optional otherwise), Etymology, Diagnosis (if there is no Comparison section), Description, Variation (optional), Comparison (if there is no Diagnosis section), Holotype (for new species descriptions), Paratypes (if any), (Other) Material examined (information about non-type material), Species included (for genera), Distribution, Habitat, Biology, other comments if appropriate. Descriptions (but not diagnoses) should be written in telegraphic style. Each genus- and species-group name mentioned should appear at least once in connection with its original authorship, but do not quote the author on each occasion, particularly in non-taxonomic papers. Do not abbreviate authors' names of animal taxa; for authors' names of plants, fungi, lichens and algae, follow Brummitt & Powell's *Authors of Plant Names* (1992) and *International Plant Names Index* or *Index fungorum*. Latin names of genus- and species-group taxa should be italicised throughout the text, including the references. Vernacular names should be accompanied by the

corresponding scientific names at the first mention. Each word in the vernacular name of a species should start with a capital letter in the text, e.g. House Sparrow, but must be lower case where no species in particular is being referred to, e.g. sparrow, sand snake.

Interpret specimen labels and geographical data consistently, using current English spelling of geographical names; old or alternative names of localities, as well as author's comments, should be given in brackets; label data of historically important or type specimens may be quoted *verbatim*. Type localities of new species must be georeferenced (supplemented with coordinates); use the degree symbol (°), not superscript °°. Depositories of the material should be given as acronyms in parentheses, and explained in the Materials and Methods section.

Example:

Holotype: ♂ SOUTH AFRICA: *Free State*: Bloemfontein district, Hopefield farm, 28°54'S 26°14'E, 28.ix.2000, C. Haddad (NHMWU).

Paratypes: 8♀, same data as holotype (NMSA).

Other material examined: ETHIOPIA: 3♂, Lake Abiata [Abiyata], 143 km S Addis Ababa [07°40'N 38°41'E], 1.iv.1962, Lund Univ[ersity]. Exp[edition]. (MZLU).

Authors are required to deposit holotypes of newly described species in nationally or internationally recognised institutions, not in private collections.

The suggested style of the genus and species chresonymies is:

Plastophorides aculeipes (Collin, 1912)

(Figs 1, 2, 4–6)

Aphiochaeta aculeipes Collin, 1912: 108, pl. 5, fig. 3. (Type locality: Seychelles)

Plastophorides aculeipes (Collin): Brues 1915: 137; Almond 2002: 148, figs 10, 11. **Syn. n.**

Sources cited in chresonymies must also be listed under References.

Identification keys should be dichotomous, with two alternatives for each character and preferably illustrated. Identification keys must be prepared using the 'Tab' key/properties, **not** the 'Numbered list' function, spaces or periods.

References:

- (a) Within the text: (Martin 1968, 1970; Dewale *et al.* 2000); Palmer (1997); Artigas and Papavero (1988); (Artigas & Papavero 1988a, b); Herbert *et al.* (2003). Use '*et al.*' for more than two authors in the text but not in the reference list. Note that references in the text should be arranged chronologically. Reference to a page number/figure(s) is cited as follows: (Collin 1930: 83, pl. 3, fig. 7). All publications referred to in the text (incl. chresonymies) must be cited in full in the list of references. Unpublished information should be cited as 'personal communication' (e.g. Green, pers. comm., 2014), 'personal observation' (pers. observ.), or article in press (Brown, in press); the last category must appear in the list of references, together with the name of the journal (or publisher, if a book) in which that work has been accepted for publication.
- (b) Under References: Arrange authors in alphabetical order, with multiple papers by the same author(s) arranged chronologically. Cite all authors and full titles. Give names of periodicals in full. Journal and book titles should be italicised. Titles of papers published in languages other than Romano-Germanic should be replaced by an English translation, with an explanatory note at the end, e.g. [in Arabic, English abstr.]. Titles of periodicals should also be translated if they appear in languages other than Romano-Germanic; they may also be given in transliteration in square brackets. Conference proceedings and dissertations should be cited as books (i.e., with place and publisher), not as periodicals. Page ranges are to be separated by an en-dash (–), not a hyphen (-). Provide DOIs or permalinks whenever possible; URLs for Internet resources are mandatory.

Examples:

Journal articles and serial publications

Brown, P.A. & Blackman, R.L. 1994. Morphometric variation in the *Geoica utricularia* (Homoptera: Aphididae) species group on *Pistacia* (Anacardiaceae), with descriptions of new species and a key to emigrant alatae. *Systematic Entomology* **19**(2): 119–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.1994.tb00582.x>

Kaunda, S.K.K. 2001. Spatial utilisation by black-backed jackals in southeastern Botswana. *African Zoology* **36**(2): 143–152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15627020.2001.11657132>

Kupfermann, I., Teyke, T., Rosen, S.C. & Weiss, K.R. 1991. Studies of behavioral state in *Aplysia*. *Biology Bulletin* **180**(2): 262–268. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1542396>

Ponomarenko, A.G. 1969. Historical development of Coleoptera Archostemata. *Transactions of the Paleontological Institute of the USSR Academy of Sciences [Trudy Paleontologicheskogo instituta Akademii nauk SSSR]* **125**: 1–239. [in Russian]

Books, book chapters and dissertations

Deacon, F. 2010. *Aspekte rakende die ruimtelike ekologie van die rooijakkals (Canis mesomelas) as probleemdiër in die Suid-Vrystaat*. MS thesis. Bloemfontein: University of the Free State. <http://hdl.handle.net/11660/835>

Kenward, R.E. 2000. *A manual for wildlife radio tagging*. London: Academic Press.

Paterson, J. 2014. Capture myopathy. **In:** West, G., Heard, D. & Caulkett, N. (Eds), *Zoo animal and wildlife immobilisation and anaesthesia*. 2nd ed. Ames, IA, USA: Wiley Blackwell, pp. 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118792919.ch12>

Taylor, L.R. & Palmer, J.M.P. 1970. Aerial sampling. **In:** van Emden, H.F. (Ed.), *Aphid technology*. London: Academic Press, pp. 125–138.

Internet resources

News Staff. 2022. New evidence suggests olive and fig trees were cultivated as early as 7,000 years ago. *SciNews* 16.07.2022. <https://www.sci.news/archaeology/olive-fig-tel-tsaf-cultivation-10910.html> (accessed 21.01.2024)

Registration with Zoobank, IPNI and Mycobank

The Editorial Office of *Indago* will register all relevant nomenclatural acts with Zoobank, IPNI and Mycobank on behalf of the authors.

Experiments on live animals

Indago will not consider papers in which the study caused unnecessary pain, discomfort or disturbance to normal health of live animals. Reports of experiments on vertebrates must state that the *Guide for the care and use of laboratory animals*, *The UFAW Handbook on the care and management of laboratory and other research animals*, or similar guidelines have been followed, as well as specific national laws where applicable. For further details, authors are urged to consult *Indago*'s Editorial Policy & Publication Ethics and Malpractice Statement.

CONTRIBUTIONS IN HUMANITIES, ARTS AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

Authors should carefully study the latest edition of *Indago* for guidance as to the conventions to be followed in the text, tables, figures, titles, legends, references, etc.

The suggested structure for original papers is: Introduction, Methodology (optional), Main text, Acknowledgements, References, Gazetteer and Appendices (if applicable), *Tables, *Figure legends. Begin the asterisked sections on new pages. Number footnotes consecutively throughout the text.

The main text should be divided into principal sections with **LEVEL 1** headings. Sub-headings should be used sparingly. Use up to three heading levels:

LEVEL 1

Level 2

Level 3

References:

The Chicago Manual of Style, with footnotes, is generally followed; a separate list of references or bibliography is optional. When a reference is used for the first time in a footnote it should be written in full^{1,2,3,4} and, for books, should include, in parentheses, the place, publisher name and year of publication^{5,6}. When references are included as a separate list, their format must follow the style of references for natural sciences contributions.

PROOFS

Proofs will be sent as a low-resolution PDF file to the corresponding or first author for correction. Authors should avoid substantial alterations of the original text at the proof stage. High-resolution PDF files are available to authors immediately upon publication of their articles.

ARTICLE PROCESSING CHARGES

Neither page charges nor submission fees are currently levied on authors, who publish in *Indago*. This includes an unlimited number of colour pages.

¹ F. van der Merwe & F. Cleophas, Mapping out an obscured South African sport history landscape through Edward Henderson history, *African Journal for Physical Health Education, Recreation and Dance* 17(2), 2011, p. 233.

² Anon., Marriage in high life, *Natal Witness*, 13.2.1872, p. 3.

³ National Museum, Bloemfontein Collection (hereafter NMB) 19486, Ex 2/12 – J. du Plessis, De La Rey Avenue, Bloemfontein.

⁴ Anon., *Harold Groves – Groves Spitfire Bows*, <http://www.vintagearchery.org/groves-archery.html> (accessed 23.10.2023).

⁵ V. de Kock, *The fun they had: The pastimes of our forefathers* (Cape Town: Howard B. Timmins, 1955), pp. 158–159.

⁶ M. Eorwine, Archery – 'Field takes off', in B. Deans (ed.), *Allied Book of South African Sport and Sports Records, 1988–89* (Randburg: SASBOR, 1989), p. 18.

INDAGO

VOLUME 35 2019

Zietsman, P.C. & Zietsman, L.E. Floristic diversity at Kolomela mine on the Ghaap Plateau, Postmasburg, Northern Cape Province	1
--	---

VOLUME 36 2020

Badenhorst, S. & Kimambo, J.S. The Frequency of Butchery Marks on Goat (<i>Capra hircus</i>) Remains from Pastoral Khoekhoe Villages at Gobabeb, Namibia	1
--	---

VOLUME 37 2021

Avenant, N.L. & Bergman, D.L. Introduction	i
De Waal H.O. Challenges in predation management – South African historical milestones	1
Kruger, Q., Avenant, N.L. & De Waal, H.O. The contribution of historical hunt club records to inform the management of damage-causing animals in South Africa	17
Van Niekerk, H.N., Bahta, Y.T. & De Waal, H.O. A review and estimation of the financial implications of livestock predation in South Africa	31
Strauss, A.J., Avenant, N.L. & De Waal, H.O. The impact of predation on Merino and Dorper sheep flocks in the central Free State Province, South Africa	43
Avenant, N.L. & Morwe, J.B. Black-backed jackal diet in the Maria Moroka Nature Reserve, Free State Province: implications for managing depredation on small stock farms	55
Green, A., Avenant, N.L. & Melville, H.I.A.S. Ranging behaviour of a territorial male Black-backed Jackal in a small stock farming area in the Southern Free State	67
Melville, H.I.A.S. & Strauss, W.M. Trialling a simple camera-trap based method to estimate Black-backed jackal population density	77

VOLUME 38 2022

Snyders, H. The cultural biography, itinerary and intersections of a second-hand artefact – The case of the Knysna Half Marathon Family Champion Tankard	1
du Bruyn, D. & Oelofse, M. The development of a gardening culture in Batho (Mangaung) from c. 1918 to 1939	9

VOLUME 39 2023–2024

Green, A., Avenant, N.L. & Melville, H.I.A.S. Getting a grip on jackals: Net-gunning as an efficient and cost-effective approach to capturing Black-backed jackals (Canidae: <i>Lupulella mesomelas</i>)	1
Terblanche, R., Kruger, Q. & de Waal, H. 'Farming with a jackal': Power relations in Black-backed jackal (Canidae: <i>Lupulella mesomelas</i>) management around the Square Kilometre Array core site in South Africa	15

INDAGO

DECEMBER 2023

VOLUME 40

ISSN 0067-9208

RESEARCH ARTICLES

HUMAN SCIENCES

“Garden areas of 50 ft. by 75 ft.”: The making of Batho as a South African “garden location” with special reference to its ornamental gardens (c. 1918–1939)

D. du Bruyn 1–22

Springboks, Spitfire bows and family archery – the National Museum Bloemfontein’s Du Plessis Collection and its national and international intersections

H. Snyders 23–34

Instructions to authors 35–38

an agency of the
Department of Sport, Arts and Culture